

Masters by Research Thesis

Performance

Session 2023/24

Philip Moore

B00411694

**Tracing the Influences, Impact and Inheritances of
Commedia dell'Arte within Shakespeare's Writing**

Supervisors: Dr Henry Bell (Lead) and Dr Catriona Fallow (Second)

17,978 Words

Acknowledgements

Firstly, I want to thank my main supervisor Dr Henry Bell for putting up with me since 2021. I never knew I would be inspired by Shakespeare until I took Henry's classes from third year when I joined UWS. My writing has been improved massively due to Henry pushing me out my comfort level of my normal writing with the feedback he has given to me over the 14 months of my dissertation. As he said to me 'That I will stop writing like a podcast presenter' and indeed I have. I also appreciate the time he gave me to have a break when needed and to perform professionally in Finland earlier in 2024 with a bunch of professional actors who were all amazing in their own rights.

Secondly, my thanks go to Dr Catriona Fellow who has also put up with me since 2022. She needs a medal. Throughout my time in Cat's classes, she has pushed me a lot and has been a very encouraging lecturer to me throughout my undergraduate and now postgraduate thesis. I do not think my thesis would be at this level without her input and feedback that she has given me. She gave me the slap on the face that I needed (not literally, just through words) to get to my end goal. I want to give a quick shout out to Dr Ann Christine Simke who has been my third supervisor who I have met during my postgraduate degree as she joined my university when I was about to complete my undergraduate. She's been a very encouraging person, and she set up the new MRes meet up session where we can get feedback and learn from each other. I think this will last a long time and it's been very useful to go to despite almost completing my MRes. The sessions have been very fun.

Thirdly, this thesis goes out to all my friends and family who have been very supportive of me throughout my time in education. From my work friends, Performance friends and friends I made in the Filmmaking and Broadcast degree. Too many people to list. Especially, my mother who was recovering from her liver cancer operation at the start of my MRes. I don't think I would have to drive and passion I would have now without them basically saying I should follow through on to my masters. Plus, Dr Stephen Collins who suggested I do the masters in the first place when he was my supervisor in my undergraduate in 2023. It also goes out to my RCS Shakespeare class in 2023 whom made me inspired as a researcher. I took this class with Shakespeare director Alasdair Hunter in late 2023, who made me appreciate Shakespeare even more and made me a confident person with it. Along with, Ayr Gaiety Young Company folks who I will be leaving in 2025.

Finally, this goes out to all the kids who get told when they are younger that won't achieve much in life. I got told this a lot when I was younger by teachers and adults due to having dyspraxia and a speech impediment. Left school with no highers. I also got told that I should drop out after my first year in college by a lecturer in 2018. Many years later I have achieved student of the year in college, got a BA (Hons) in Performance, about to complete an MRes in Performance and now I'm a professional actor & writer. Keep pushing kids, don't let words hurt you. One day you will achieve your dreams. Keep going x

Ethics & Plagiarism

Ethical Considerations (No Participants)

This study did not involve the use of Human Participants in the collection of data. There was, therefore, no application made for ethical approval to the Module Coordinator.

Plagiarism Statement

I confirm that by signing, dating and submitting this dissertation, I have read, understood and accepted the University's regulations in relation to Cheating and Plagiarism.

Signed

Name

Philip Moore

Date

19th December 2024

Table of Contents

Abstract	p.5
Introduction.....	p.6
Chapter Breakdown.....	p.7
Methodology.....	p.8
Literature Review.....	p.9
Chapter One: Tracing the influence of <i>Commedia dell'Arte lazzi</i> in Shakespeare's comedies: an exploration of <i>The Comedy of Errors</i> & <i>A Midsummer Night's Dream</i>.....	p.10
Shakespeare's Playscripts: Inheritors of Comic Conditions.....	p.11
<i>The Comedy of Errors</i>	p.14
<i>A Midsummer Night's Dream</i>	p.22
Chapter Two: Will Kempe: <i>Commedia dell'Arte's</i> Influence on his Improvisation and its Impact on Shakespeare's Writing	p.31
Kempe's Biography: Influences, Impact and Inheritors.....	p.32
Kempe and Shakespeare: Improviser vs Writer.....	p.35
Kempe: Conditioned by <i>commedia dell'arte</i>	p.39
Conclusions: Kempe's Small Parts but Bigger Presence.....	p.43
Conclusion: Shakespeare: an inheritor of <i>commedia dell'arte</i> to the last	p.44
Findings and Future Research.....	p.47
Reference List	p.48

ABSTRACT

William Shakespeare's work and the Italian theatre style of *commedia dell'arte* may appear to be two different styles but they are linked through the work of Will Kempe, who was a member of the Lord Chamberlain's Men with Shakespeare. The aim of this thesis is to identify the ways in which Shakespeare's work was possibly inspired by *commedia dell'arte*. By using close reading and New Historicism and building on the work of Shakespeare scholars such as Kathleen Lea, Andrew Grewer and Robert Henke scholar, I investigate the performance conditions of Shakespeare's texts, through the lens of Early Modern England looking at the various contemporary styles that Shakespeare drew on and argue that *commedia* was very much a part of the performance landscape at the time. I argue that many elements of *commedia* can be seen throughout Shakespeare's most famous plays and that it is likely that Will Kempe's improvisational techniques were drawn from improvisational stage performances by touring Italian troupes of the time.

INTRODUCTION

This study will make the case for understanding the Italian theatre style *commedia dell'arte* as a key component of William Shakespeare's performance language with the added exploration of Kempe's performance practise that was used in his work as a performer. Many scholars such as Kathleen Lea (1962), Andrew Grewer (1989) and Robert Henke (1996) debate if there was a direct, historic link between Shakespeare and *commedia dell'arte*. Some scholars such as Henri Grégoire (1940) do not believe the facts presented of the direct link with *commedia* and Shakespeare, although, Lea, Grewer and Henke pinpoint evidence of Shakespeare work of using elements from *commedia dell'arte*. By contrast, of the *commedia* troupes were performing in England in 1578 when Shakespeare was very young. He would have heard of the performances or may have seen them when he was a young child.

My own approach will move the discussion away from pinpointing moments in Shakespeare's biography to discover moments of direct connection with *commedia dell'arte* troupes and, instead, treat the Shakespeare plays as blueprints for performances that were themselves products of the performance conditions of their time with *commedia dell'arte* being a one of the key elements of the conditions. In doing so, I am seeking to move away from the view of Shakespeare's work being referred to as a singular 'genius' that people thought he was and I am detangling his artistry as a theatre maker's point of view. To do this, I will utilise two main approaches to explore and contribute to this scholarly debate: firstly, a historical exploration of Will Kempe's *commedia dell'arte*-informed career and performance style with the Lord Chamberlain's Men will illustrate how Shakespeare's work is an historical example of the standard shown within the theatre company. Kempe's practise is analysed due to sources of him using improvisational in Shakespeare's plays in Lord Chamberlain Men which is adding to the argument that *commedia* was evidential in Shakespeare's company. Secondly, by connecting close reading of the texts to the conditions in which some of Shakespeare's plays were written, the study will unearth the traces of *commedia dell'arte* characterisation, plot lines, themes and, most crucial to this thesis, stage business that are present in comedies – *The Comedy of Errors* (1594), *A Midsummer Night's Dream* (1596/1597) and *The Tempest* (1611) – and the tragedies – *Romeo and Juliet* (1595) and *Titus Andronicus* (1591),¹ A fundamental component of the stage language of *commedia dell'arte* present in the plays of Shakespeare considered in this study are *lazzi* and the dramaturgical connections between them and the plays will be considered throughout.

Although, with the focus on *commedia*, the influence of other forms of folk performance that was happening in Early Modern London must be credited to the culture that was happening at the time as they were coming through alongside *commedia* when Shakespeare was developing his work. The folk performance of mummers is a high example of the culture in Early Modern London as mummers

¹ All the dates given in this thesis with Shakespeare's playtext is sourced by Royal Shakespeare Company website. (Royal Shakespeare Company, 2017)

“which was enacted the wooing or marriage surviving from ancient pagan rituals in European folklore’ (Baskervill, 1924, p.1) much like *lazzis* in *commedia dell’arte* that were used in Shakespeare’s texts that will be analysed in the thesis. Mummers was a common tradition in the British isles in that period.

Chapter Breakdown

In my first chapter, I will unearth traces of the influence of *commedia dell’arte* beyond the presence of Will Kempe in two of Shakespeare’s comedies. This will draw focus to the presence of *lazzi*, another key element of *commedia dell’arte*’s performance language in *The Comedy of Errors* and *A Midsummer Night’s Dream*. A close reading of these texts, side-by-side with accounts of *lazzi*, will enable me to evidence the influence of *commedia dell’arte* in the texts which were created as blueprints for performance. A key source for this approach is the descriptions and analysis of *lazzi* from Mel Gordon’s Book *The Comic Routines of the Commedia dell’Arte* (2001).

In my second chapter, I will explore Kempe’s relationship with *commedia dell’arte* and make the case for him as a key factor in the impact of the theatrical form on Shakespeare during his time as part of the Lord Chamberlain’s. Here, I will explore his work as an actor, clown and public celebrity in Early Modern England and place him in a lineage of comic performers that began with Richard Tarlton and ended with Kempe’s own replacement in Shakespeare’s company, Robert Armin. This biographical examination is undertaken to further my argument that Shakespeare’s writing process was informed by the performance traditions and conditions created by the actors around him. I will draw upon existing scholarship that speculates on the reasons behind the abrupt end of this working relationship as a way of highlighting how Kempe’s influence is evident as much by his absence from the company as from his presence.

Through the presence of this stage language, I will also explore connections between characterisation in Shakespeare’s writing and the *commedia dell’arte* characters of Zanni, Magnifico, Il Capitano, Pantalone and the unmasked Lover characters of the Italian theatre form. Finally, I will consider Shakespeare as an inheritor of scenarios and plotlines used within *commedia dell’arte* and *lazzi* themes.

Beyond this historical and biographical approach, I explore the textual elements contained in *Titus Andronicus* and *Romeo and Juliet* and the short jigs written and performed by Kempe after performances of Shakespeare’s plays to speculate on the *commedia dell’arte*-informed performance practice that Kempe used. This will address the ‘underwriting’ of comic parts to point to evidence of key elements of the stage language of *commedia dell’arte* like improvisation and comic stage business such as slapstick. In order to do this, I will draw my main focus towards the analysing the character of Peter in *Romeo and Juliet* and the Clown in *Titus Andronicus* to explore how Kempe’s presence impacted and influenced the play.

In the conclusion to this thesis, I will summarise my findings through an examination of the remaining influence of *commedia dell'arte* in what is believed to be Shakespeare's final single authored play, *The Tempest* (1611). I will make the case that, despite this being Shakespeare's last comedy written many years after Kempe's exit from the company, it contains some of the strongest evidence of *commedia's lazzi* out of all of the texts. I will consider to what extent Shakespeare's plays contain a permanent inheritance of the Italian performance style and this research can be of value to contemporary theatre practitioners and scholars in the 21st Century.

Methodology

Throughout this thesis, I am using close reading to unearth the traces of *commedia dell'arte lazzi*, characterisation and wordplay in Shakespeare's plays. The use of close reading is effective as "the reader has to develop a fairly sophisticated understanding of what the author actually said" (Frey, Fisher, 2013, p.1) which is useful in expanding and analysing the links of *commedia dell'arte* with Shakespeare's texts. Close reading is "a technically informed, fine-grained analysis of some piece of writing, usually in connection with some broader question of interest." (Smith, p.58, 2016) which is relevant to connect the links between *commedia* and Shakespeare. Alongside this methodological approach, historical research will be used to investigate the performance conditions of Shakespeare's writing, particularly the comedic performance traditions that were present in Early Modern England and, specifically in the company of Lord Chamberlain's Men/Kings Men, with the aforementioned actor Will Kempe. I consider this historical information from a New Historicist perspective, New Historicism being a method which is a "hugely influential approach to literature, especially in studies of William Shakespeare's works and literature of the Early Modern period." (Parvini, 2017, n.p). This movement itself is a product of Cultural Materialism and both these approaches include the point of view of Shakespeare as a cultural figure and his plays as cultural products which were a result of the conditions of creation. My approach will examine *commedia dell'arte* research literature side-by-side with remaining records of Shakespeare's texts and accounts of contemporary performance. The approach that is being undertaken is viewing Shakespeare's writing as a historical, text-based analysis but is rooted within the practice of *commedia's* elements.

Throughout, I engage with secondary sources rather than archival sources. There are a number of reasons for this choice. Firstly, the MRes project is a year, which limits the amount of time available for original research. Secondly, part of the rationale for the project is to engage with the scholarship on Shakespeare and *commedia dell'arte* and push the academic conversations forward in this area. As there are only a few contemporary accounts of Shakespeare's performances or *commedia dell'arte* performances through diaries that I discuss later, I largely rely on secondary academic accounts to develop my argument.

In order to briefly clarify and position my study within these movements, I would like to define the term Cultural Materialism methodology as a “practise grows from an eclectic body of work in Britain in the post-war period which can be broadly characterised as cultural analysis” (Dollimore and Sinfield, 1985, p.2). The cultural analysis in this thesis considers *commedia dell’arte* links with Shakespeare’s plays in performance through the text themselves and historical performance practices to see how figures such as Kempe inspired the creation of the plays. Dollimore and Sinfield (1985) add that Cultural Materialism’s ‘work is part of an important perspective which has come to be called new historicism, a perspective concerned generally with the interaction in this period between State power and cultural forms.’ (p.3). The key term in this approach for my study is ‘cultural forms’ and the cultural forms here that I am connecting are both *commedia dell’arte* and the Elizabethan/Jacobean theatre movement. Scholars like Dollimore have applied this critical theory to Shakespeare Studies as a whole object and I am suggesting that *commedia* is one of those crucial environmental elements in the creation of Shakespeare’s texts.

My study adopts the approach of another key cultural materialist, Graham Holderness who considered the creation of Shakespeare’s work as “a collaborative cultural process in which plays were made by writers, theatrical entrepreneurs, architects and craftsmen, actors and audience” (Holderness, 1998, p.12). This position acknowledges the potential for Shakespeare’s plays to be understood as not singular entities, but open to and constructed by people such as Kempe who himself was influenced by *commedia dell’arte*. Both Cultural Materialism and New Historicist methods work together since they share a common preoccupation with the relationship between literature and history as it understands the function of the texts that will aid the methodology (Harris, 2003, p.3).

Literature Review

The importance of *commedia dell’arte* in Shakespeare’s writing has been highlighted by Grewer who suggests, “it is widely acknowledged that he drew on contemporary Italian plays as a source for incident and plot [...] Shakespeare’s immediate dramatic model appears to have been the *Commedia dell’Arte*” (Grewer, 2014, p.1). Far from the ‘singular genius’ creating work away from the influence of other theatre forms like *commedia dell’arte* or actors such as Kempe, Robert Greene, a contemporary of Shakespeare and a popular author in Elizabethan London, described Shakespeare as an ‘Upstart Crow’ as “Greene [was] outraged that Shakespeare, a common actor, ha[d] overstepped some social and educational barrier” due to Shakespeare appearing to be above his station due to his lack of education and plagiarism of his various plays. (Vickers, 2017, p.3). In a passage written by Henry Chettle in 1592 “thus blames Shakespeare for his proud self-confidence and his plagiarizing habits” as Chettle goes on to highlight lines from *Henry VI* (1591) as evidence that Shakespeare did not originate his work (Chiari, 2014, p.143). Peter W. Dickson argues that “some poems attributed to Shakespeare were actually composed by others” (Dickson, Becker, p.12, 2023) which causes

problems when attributing specific works to Shakespeare and considering whether he can be considered a singular genius or a product of a rich and fluid literary context. Ben Jonson who was known as Shakespeare's rival as a playwright wrote in a poem that, "Shakespeare's writings cannot be praised too much" (Dickson, Becker, p.15, 2023). Jonson later added: "Shakespeare's mind and manners brightly shines," at which he seems "to shake a lance brandish'd at the eyes of ignorance." (Dickson, Becker p.16, 2023). Holderness (1988) argues the Cultural Materialist perspective that, in Shakespeare's plays, it is important to challenge the narrative "when addressing the work of a Renaissance dramatist, on the clarity and simplicity of a direct, controlling relationship between author and written text" (p.12).

As mentioned above, Henke, Lea and Grewer are the key scholars who have engaged with *commedia dell'arte* and the theatre style of Shakespeare. Robert Henke (1996) states that "Both theaters drew on audiences of a wide socioeconomic range, including those who could read and those who could not." (p.224) Henke (1996) adds that '*commedia dell'arte* should be intrinsically interesting to students of oral culture, because it was not performed from set scripts but instead used as a basis for improvisational performance a system of established character types and a rough plot outline" (p.225). Andrew Grewer mentions that the connection between *commedia* and Shakespeare is speculative due to the evidence that remains in books, articles and other forms of research. Of *Two Gentlemen of Verona* (1590/91) for example, Grewer states "In the first place, the entire cast of characters is not only obviously "Italian," it is immediately reminiscent of the set of stock types of the *commedia dell'arte*. The two pairs of young lovers, Valentine and Silvia, Proteus and Julia, are the innamorati. Valentine's foolish, boastful rival, Thurio, plays a role equivalent to that of the capitano" (Grewer, 1998, p.28) By seeing the scholars work, though what speculative as mentioned by Grewer. The hints of *commedia* is starting to show through the hints in Shakespeare's work. David Wiles (1992) work in Shakespeare's clowning will be examined in terms of Kempe's connection to *commedia dell'arte* and the use of clowning that he used in various characters in Shakespeare's play such as Peter in *Romeo and Juliet* which is one of the main focuses I am analysing in the thesis. I am building on this work and analysing Will Kempe's relationship with *commedia dell'arte*.

CHAPTER 1

Tracing the influence of Commedia dell'Arte lazzi in Shakespeare's comedies: an exploration of *The Comedy of Errors* & *A Midsummer Night's Dream*

My analysis of William Kempe's performance style on the creation of Shakespeare's work demonstrated briefly in the introduction, his plays were the product of multiple conditions of which the playwright was a part. The *commedia dell'arte lazzi*, defined in the introduction to this thesis and in this chapter, are a key textual clue as to the Italian theatre style having a key impact in the performance and writing of the comedic texts that Shakespeare wrote. In this chapter a central

question that will be addressed is how can the exploration of *lazzi* help to define the influence of *commedia dell'arte* Shakespeare's comedies? Away from the technical, physical comedy of *lazzi* I will also ask what does the presence of comic plot lines and characters reminiscent of *commedia dell'arte* scenarios tell us about the multitude of influences on Shakespeare's writing? And, moreover, how did these comic inheritances enhance the writing when performed?

Shakespeare's Playscripts: Inheritors of Comic Conditions

Steel (2017) mentions that "Shakespeare's knowledge of Italian literature is well documented" (p.2) and whilst *commedia dell'arte* was not a literature form in definition as it was a theatre style that did not use scripts until later on when Goldoni introduced them to the troupes, Steel's thoughts are evidence that Italian culture was a key part of the cultural conditions of which Shakespeare was a part. This chapter will suggest that it is clear in his early comedies such as *The Comedy of Errors* and *A Midsummer Night's Dream* that *commedia dell'arte* was a central influence with evidence of many the *lazzi* used in scenes in these plays. The *lazzi* used in *commedia dell'arte* could have come into Shakespeare's knowledge into the mixture culture in London, England in his earlier years as a playwright: London was a major European port at that the time where residents – Shakespeare included – could have encountered aspects of Italian culture second-hand. For example, Giovanni Boccaccio's writing and other Italian writers can be seen in some of the plots of Shakespeare's plays such as *The Merchant of Venice* (1596/1597). Boccaccio, himself influenced by *commedia dell'arte*, played an important role in the Italian literary tradition in the fourteenth century through *Decameron* (Eisner, 2013, p.2). Although, Steel makes the main claim of *commedia dell'arte*, he mentions that Shakespeare might have overheard or been part of the conversation from someone who knew Italian in England. Whether or not Shakespeare had direct knowledge of the *lazzi*, characters and plot lines of *commedia dell'arte* is hard to concretely ascertain but Eisner suggests that "Shakespeare almost certainly heard accounts of the Martinelli visit only a decade earlier" (2013, p.30). Drusiano and Tristano Matnielli were the leaders of an Italian troupe who performed *commedia dell'arte*. Tristano was one of the first known actors to perform *Arlecchino* to a crowd outside of Italy (Schrickx, 1976, p.5). But before going in further context with the links with Shakespeare and *commedia dell'arte*, what is *commedia dell'arte*?

Commedia dell'arte was a theatre form "in which actors improvised upon a scenario (a play synopsis), arose in the middle of the sixteenth century and continued until the latter part of the eighteenth century" (Schmitt, 2004, p.2). It originated in Italy and was a popular and adaptable theatre form which used improvisation, almost became lost as audiences started to lose interest in it as they found it dull as the same performances were happening in each performance until Carlo Goldoni formalised many of the scenario and characters into his scripts which were themselves influential on

European theatre such as pantomimes with the plots of love that took place. (de Colle, Freeman, Parmar, de Collie, 2015, n.p).

Commedia began on the streets and marketplaces across Renaissance Italy since it was “easier to attract an audience and make a profit.” (D’Anna, 2019, p.36) as theatres were not as accessible to the full range of social classes in Italy during this period. *Commedia dell’arte* is mainly an improvisation form and much of the content of this improvisation is dependent on audience reaction. Olly Crick (2022) states “There is no fourth wall in commedia, so direct address to an audience (with the possibility of reply) may be responded to directly: “The audience is an active, responsive partner” (Fava, 2007: xiv)” (p.127). The fluidity of textual definition in *commedia dell’arte* was also dependent on the location of the performance, by making local references to the area(s) surrounding the particular audiences. As Crick notes, “Altering planned stage dialogue to include references to local places and events as long as these events and places are included within the action of the unfolding performance can create a positive response from the spectators” (2022, p.128).

Commedia dell’arte is also known for its masked, stock characters to help distinguish who they were on stage to an audience that would recognise many of these standardised, popular figures. Rudlin (1997) highlights why the use of mask was important “in commedia dell’arte, by virtue of its derivation from Carnival [...] the personality of the actor is thus overtaken not by an author’s scripter character, but by the persona of the mask to be played” (p.34). Each stock character, therefore, had certain characterisations and stage traditions which each performer had to learn, develop and make their own.

The theatre form’s long term and far-reaching footprint outside of Italy is considered by Schmitt (2004) who believes, “The long-lived success of the form had to do with its ability to accommodate the particulars of the various audiences and playing conditions: nobility and commoners” (p.3). This influence of *commedia* in the last century through the writing, impacting upon people such as “Shakespeare, Ben Jonson, Goldoni, Gozzi, Moliere [...] and performers Charlie Chaplin and Dario Fo.” (Schmitt, 2009, p.299) whereas Dario Fo is the most modern performer listed, retain an influence over contemporary actors, performers and writers in 21st century through the historical figures like Ben Jonson. One such trace of the influence that can be seen to this day is that, in its early stages, *commedia dell’arte* was only performed by men. The Dame character in UK pantomimes, therefore, is a direct inheritor of this via *commedia dell’arte*’s influence on French theatre from the 18th Century. The debate concerning Shakespeare’s direct interaction with *commedia* began with scholar Kathleen Lea (1962) followed by Allardyce Nicoll in 1963 (Pugliatti, 2016, p.1). Lea “made a case for his use of scenario” (Gilvary, 2004, p.15) with *commedia dell’arte* and *lazzi* but she did not directly state or make exact evidence if Shakespeare saw *commedia dell’arte* in person or not as he

was a child at the time when the *commedia dell'arte* troupes came across to England momentarily “between 1573 and 1578” (Henke, 2018, p.115).

The evidence behind Shakespeare’s direct interaction with *commedia dell'arte* troupes when he was young is circumstantial, so it is important to look beyond the historical to trace the influence of the theatre form. This can be done through analysing the links within his performance style, scripts, characterisation, plot and the wordplay that Shakespeare uses in his plays that are performed. In doing so, I am treating the plays as a material cultural product that was designed to be performed – the performances themselves were an inheritance of the variety of styles and fashions of which Shakespeare and his colleagues were a part. Whilst the text provides many clues to trace this influence, it is important to acknowledge that, if Shakespeare’s scripts are and were blueprints for the performance, this in the spirit of Steel who suggests the Lord Chamberlain’s Men was “like the *commedia dell'arte* players, cared so much and no more for the sanctities of his set down script.” (Steele, 1977, p.210). As I highlight in the next chapter, Kempe, a key member of the company, was like a performer in a *commedia dell'arte* troupes who often improvised in the performances when noticing audiences were getting bored of the script performed. By focusing on *The Comedy of Errors* (1594) and *A Midsummer Night’s Dream* (1595/96) plays written by Shakespeare when Kempe was in the company and where, therefore, I have established the traces of the theatre form through the English comic actor’s influence.

Throughout this chapter, my methodological approach will be aligned with Holderness and Terry Hawkes who observes that the “notion of a single “authoritative” text, immediately expressive of the plenitude of its author’s mind and meaning, would have been unfamiliar to Shakespeare, involved as he was in the collaborative enterprise of dramatic production” (Holderness, 1998, p.12). In this sense “the object of study is not its text and its context, not literature and its history, but rather literature *in* history” (Harris, 2003, p.3) – the ‘history’ in my case being the performance history and the influences surrounding these performances present in Shakespeare’s texts, particularly the plotlines, characterisation and *lazzi* of *commedia dell'arte*. In *commedia dell'arte*, a *lazzo* is an improvised scenario performed outside of the main plot of the play by certain characters to elevate the scene for the audience’s enjoyment. The word *lazzi* has multiple meanings surrounding the word on the function it is being used commedia. Luigi Riccoboni suggests the *lazzi* “alluded to the comic business that tied together the performance.” (Gordon, 2001, p.4). Riccoboni means that the *lazzi* served as an independent routine that was not interrupted or unravelled the commedia plots or the performance of the style during the performance. Mel Gordon (2001) describes the definition of the *lazzi* as described by Perrucci “something foolish, witty, or metaphorical in word or action.” These *lazzi*, from a narrative perspective could be seen as pausing the flow of the plot and were often used when the audiences were considered to be bored of a scene by the performers who had experience of rehearsing and delivering them over the history of their companies (Gordon, 2001, p.4).

The Comedy of Errors

The Comedy of Errors was believed to have been written in 1594 and is, therefore, considered to be one of Shakespeare's first comedies. (Royal Shakespeare Company, 2017, n.p) The influence of Roman Comedy is clear to the central role that the master/servant characters play, which is reminiscent of plays such as *Epidicus* and *Eunuchus* written by the Roman Comedians Plautus and Terence between 205 BCE and 161 BC. "*The Comedy of Errors*, is a brilliant variation on a theme by the Roman playwright Plautus, which Elizabethan schoolchildren often more subtly and pervasively interfused in Shakespeare's works" (Greenblatt, Cohen, 2015, p.48). Both Shakespeare and *commedia dell'arte* were inspired by Plautus and Terence in their approaches and are, in this sense, inheritors of that ancient comic tradition. As "commedia erudita, the learned comedy of the period, based on Greek and Roman comedy, can tell us much about the *commedia dell'arte*" (Schmitt, 2004, p.56). It influenced *commedia dell'arte* on the way it is written. For the purpose of this section of my study, I am going to be focusing on the main character dynamic between the two sets of twins present in the play: the Antipholus pair (Antipholus of Syracuse and Antipholus of Ephesus) and the two Dromio (Dromio of Syracuse and Dromio of Ephesus) characters.

The story of *The Comedy of Errors* begins with the story of how Egeon was separated from his twin sons and their twin servants in a shipwreck. One pair of son and servant, who were raised in Syracuse, Antipholus and his slave Dromio, go to try and find brothers in Ephesus. The other set of son and servant, who have the same names, live in Ephesus and, when the other Antipholus and Dromio arrive from Syracuse, a series of comic incidents involving mistaken identity and slapstick comedy such as the 'door knocking' scene in III.i (which is explored below) ensue. At the end of the play, the twins find each other after a series of absurdly coincidental events. The parents reunite and all the problems created earlier within the play are seemingly resolved within the Ephesus community.

As can already be traced in the plot summarised above, the play has connections with *commedia dell'arte* within the plot and characters, particularly the master/servant relationships that are explored. As highlighted in the introduction to this thesis, in *commedia dell'arte*, one of the key servant characters is Zanni.

Figure 1. Zanni, the smart servant. (Moscatello, n.d)

Zanni's mask "originated with the mountain people who descended to Bergamo to make their fortunes in the city" (De Luca, 1983, p.8) and Zanni is known for being a servant with the lowest social status in a *commedia* character structure. Zanni represents "laziness, immoderate appetite (gluttony), insolence, unrefinement, rudeness, crudeness and, at times, shrewdness" (De Luca, 1983, p.8). The shrewdness characteristic came to light in later developments of *commedia dell'arte* and became a main trait of Zanni's character. Zanni's role within a *commedia* scenario is to oversee love affairs for his master. Zanni is "the performer of the elaborate 'lazzi' effortlessly carrying out his tricks, antics and comic turns" and, as such, has an important impact on Shakespeare's inheritance of the theatre form (De Luca, 1983, p.9). In my study I connect Kempe's acting style with the Zanni figure, arguing that his portrayal of servant figures is part of this comic lineage. Furthermore, Zanni is "essentially the focal point of the *commedia dell'arte*; without his anti-heroic presence no *commedia* could be sustained to such lengths" (De Luca, 1983, p.9). As explored in Chapter 1, the figures of the Dromio twins in *The Comedy of Errors* and Puck in *A Midsummer Night's Dream* are presented as being formed out of the influence of Zanni's cultural legacy. *A Midsummer Night's Dream* will be analysed in the next sub-heading. In Chapter 2, Kempe's status as the focal point in Shakespeare's play resulted in tensions and his eventually exit from the company.

Often storylines involving Zanni include his poor treatment at the hands of his master, one such character being Magnifico, and these moments often involve slapstick humour such as the "lazzi of bargaining, often between Zanni and Magnifico; these delay the action but are still part of the play" (Royce, 1986, p.82).

Figure 2. Magnifico's costume (Naccari, 2014)

Magnifico's mask "represents the ridiculed old man who falls in love frequently and foolishly" (De Luca, 1983, p.9), which in turn represents the Venetian merchants that are in Italy. Magnifico has a powerful presence in a scenario with his movements and how he acts towards servant characters such as Zanni – this master/servant relationship.

In relation to *The Comedy of Errors*, the two Dromios experience similar fates to Zanni, albeit sometimes for reasons of mistaken identity. In II.i Dromio of Ephesus says tells Adriana and Luciana a story about what the person he believed to be his master said (when in fact it was actually the identical twin of his master). Adriana's response highlights how violence is often the first tool used to discipline Dromio for not following the orders or instructions of his masters:

ADRIANA

Back, slave, or I will break thy pate across.

DROMIO OF EPHEBUS

And he will bless that cross with other beating:
Between you I shall have a holy head.

ADRIANA

Hence, prating peasant! fetch thy master home.

(II.i)

At this stage, some editions state that Adriana beats Dromio on his exit, and productions often make this choice. This is the same stage language of *commedia dell'arte* scenario involving Zanni who is often beaten up by another character for disobeying them on what they said to them. A prime example

in one of the lazzi such as “Lazzi of the Sack (II)... Zanni [or Arlecchino] hides in a sack, which the Captain [or Scaramouche] trips over and begins to beat in anger” (Gordon, 2001, p.14) As shown in the text, the character of Adriana says the word ‘slave’ to Dromio of Ephesus drawing a parallel with the master and servant relationship in *commedia*. In this case, in Shakespeare’s play Adriana is the master, owing to her marriage to his master, Antipholus of Ephesus, whilst Dromio is the slave to Adriana’s household.

This combination of the master/servant relationship, mistaken identity and comic violence, or to use a technical phrase, slapstick, enables connections to be drawn with *The Comedy of Errors* and some *commedia dell’arte lazzi*. One such *lazzo* rooted in this character interaction and stage business is the “Lazzo of “Have You Eaten?” As Gordon states, in the *lazzo*, “Pulcinella responds by asking them [Zanni] if they have eaten. They say yes. Pulcinella repeats the question several times and they beat him” (Gordon, 2001, p.27). There is more concrete textual evidence for this influence earlier in the play in I.ii where Dromio of Ephesus mistakes Antipholus of Syracuse for his master. Traces of the *lazzo* can be unearthed in the scene when Antipholus and Dromio ask each other multiple questions, which result in Antipholus of Syracuse beating Dromio of Ephesus:

DROMIO OF EPHEBUS:

I have some marks of yours upon my pate,
Some of my mistress' marks upon my shoulders,
But not a thousand marks between you both.
If I should pay your worship those again,
Perchance you will not bear them patiently.

ANTIPHOLUS OF SYRACUSE:

Thy mistress' marks? what mistress, slave, hast thou?

DROMIO OF EPHEBUS:

Your worship's wife, my mistress at the Phoenix;
She that doth fast till you come home to dinner,
And prays that you will hie you home to dinner.

ANTIPHOLUS OF SYRACUSE:

What, wilt thou flout me thus unto my face,
Being forbid? There, take you that, sir knave!

(II.i)

In this case, Dromio can be seen as a Zanni figure: in *commedia dell’arte* Zanni often gets beaten up for doing something that he/she should have not done which has angered their master. In *The Comedy of Errors*, it is Antipholus who is confused by his servant Dromio without knowing that he is speaking to the wrong Dromio in the first place.

Slapstick is just one example of the parallels between the fundamental stage language of *commedia dell'arte* and *The Comedy of Errors*. Further potential connection can be unearthed when reading III.i from the play next to the “Lazzo of the Inside”. This *lazzo* involves, “Pulcinella, hidden from the Captain by a door, speaks in several fake voices, such as servants begging Pulcinella not to beat them anymore” (Gordon, 2001, p.42). In this moment in the play, known as the ‘door knocking scene’, there is a mix up of identity on a grand comic scale. Antipholus of Syracuse, only newly in Ephesus for the first time, is inside the house dining with Adriana (who considers him to be her wife). When Antipholus of Ephesus arrives with a goldsmith, he expects to be let into the house. Dromio of Syracuse (also new to the town and seeking to look after his master) is within the house on the other side of the door refuses to let them in and believes Dromio of Ephesus to have stolen his name:

DROMIO OF SYRACUSE:

[Within] Nor to-day here you must not; come again

when you may.

ANTIPHOLUS OF EPHEBUS:

What art thou that keepest me out from the house I owe?

DROMIO OF SYRACUSE:

[Within] The porter for this time, sir, and my name is Dromio.

DROMIO OF EPHEBUS:

O villain! thou hast stolen both mine office and my name.

The one ne'er got me credit, the other mickle blame.

If thou hadst been Dromio to-day in my place,

Thou wouldst have changed thy face for a name or thy

name for an ass.

(III, I)

Whilst there is a difference between the *lazzo* and the Shakespeare text in that the variety of voices from behind the door are all spoken as the true characters, there is clear dramaturgical influence between the two performance methods. The confusion created by the mix up of identity surrounding the door-focussed stage business is moved away from impersonations in the scene and instead are driven by the use of the double pair of identical twins. This is a good example of how Shakespeare and his company took ideas from other cultural forms, such as *commedia dell'arte*, but developed

them into their own performance traditions. Another possible reason for this choice is the potential of one actor playing both twins. As highlighted in the previous chapter, Kempe was a member of the company during this period and having him play both Dromio characters could be seen as an opportunity for him to improvise and showcase his physical comedic abilities.

III.i contains more traces of *commedia dell'arte* in the stage business that the script is a blueprint for. The focus on door knocking has more roots in *lazzi* particularly the “Lazzo of “Go Back and Knock!” described by Gordon thus, “The Captain takes Pulcinella for a servant in Pulcinella’s house. The Captain asks Pulcinella for Pulcinella. Pulcinella replies, “Go back and knock!” The Captain does so. This repeats several times” (Gordon, 2001, p.37). This, like Shakespeare’s writing, makes a playful use of a door of an inn a central part of the scene and functions as a way of the ‘master’ character lose status. In Shakespeare’s play *Antipholus of Ephesus* is refused entry to his house by his own wife, thus dramatically losing status in front of the Goldsmith and his own slave, Dromio:

ADRIANA

[Within] Who is that at the door that keeps all this noise?

DROMIO OF SYRACUSE

[Within] By my troth, your town is troubled with unruly boys.

ANTIPHOLUS OF EPHEBUS

Are you there, wife? you might have come before.

ADRIANA

[Within] Your wife, sir knave! go get you from the door.

(III.i)

Again, Shakespeare takes inspiration from the *lazzo* but does not copy it entirely. Whilst in the *commedia dell'arte* set up The Captain mistakes Pulcinella for a servant, in *The Comedy of Errors* it is Adriana who believes Antipholus of Ephesus to be an ‘unruly boy’ as Dromio describes him. On stage, there is plenty of opportunity for the actors, mostly likely including Kempe, to improvise and use physical comedy. The actor playing the Ephesus twin outside of the door might make a battering ram of props and try to break down the door that is holding them from the truth which Luce is not letting them into to. Or Dromio himself, likely played by Kempe, could become this battering ram. The likelihood of Kempe playing this part can be traced to his previous work in comic servant roles, such as Peter in *Romeo and Juliet* which will be explored in Chapter 2. The idea of the battering ram can be seen in The Globe’s 2014 production of *The Comedy of Errors* when Dromio of Ephesus played by Jamie Wilkes runs out of ideas on how to get into the house after trying to squeeze in

through the door, runs himself into the door hoping it will open but it fails to do so. (Drama Online, n.d) Again, these traces of performance styles and the understanding of the material conditions of performance highlight the multiple influences that could have been at play with the writing of Shakespeare's play. Unearthing these clues also give researchers and theatre makers inspiration for how these scenes can be staged today, my exploration of the 'battering ram' being one example of this.

Having considered the master/servant relationship, comedic violence and the connections between door business and *commedia dell'arte* I would like to finish my exploration of *The Comedy of Errors* by addressing the thematic connections between Shakespeare's writing and the Italian performance style. Both 'searching' and 'confusion' are important aspects that are considered in a variety of ways across the play that are also a central point of many *lazzi* in *commedia dell'arte*. In V.i, for example, Antipholus of Ephesus perhaps best sums up the increasingly frenzied sense of confusion that drives the tempo and tone of the comedy in his summary of the events of the play (V.i.214-254). This speaks to the "Lazzo Of "There's No Knowledge!" (Gordon, 2001, p.26) where, in this *lazzo*, Pantalone is confused by strange events and tricks that have happened to him lately. It causes Pantalone act strangely and become worked up about the events which have happened to him but no one else understands.

Figure 3. Pantalone's illustration. (Sand, 2024)

The Pantalone mask "has white eyebrows and moustache to show his oldness, he takes in when people move past him with thoughts and purpose" (Fava, Rudlin, 1993). Pantalone, according to Fava is thought to be Magnifico's former self due to the power he used to have whilst he was younger. Pantalone is described as "an elderly Venetian dressed in red, who was the father, husband or guardian" (Pennel, 1986, p.8). Pantalone's character traits can be compared to the lustful characters across Shakespeare's plays such as in *Midsummer Night's Dream* with Demetrius.

There are traces of this in Antipholus of Ephesus' speech since he is saying he did not do all of the actions that people are accusing him of – again, there are clues for performance by considering the influence of *commedia dell'arte* here. Perhaps the actor playing this role can treat the speech as a gradual build, reminiscent of the *lazzo* which ends with the character shouting and confused and to be exhausted and unhinged when he delivers the final section, 'I gained my freedom, and immediately / Ran thither to your grace, whom I beseech / To give me ample satisfaction / For these deep shames and great indignities' (V.i.249-253).

In terms of 'searching' – this theme can be seen in the stage language that Shakespeare works with, itself informed potentially by a specific *lazzo* seen in Shakespeare's writing. In "Lazzo of Searching [...] The lovers, Clori and Sireno, search for one another. But each time one leaves the stage, the other appears" (Gordon, 2001, p.42). This device is utilised by Shakespeare multiple times - it happens immediately when Antipholus of Syracuse and Dromio of Syracuse are first introduced in Act 1, Scene 2. Dromio of Syracuse exits the stage after commands from Antipholus of Ephesus while Dromio of Ephesus mistakes Antipholus of Syracuse as his master when he arrives:

ANTIPHOLUS OF SYRACUSE:

He that commends me to mine own content
Commends me to the thing I cannot get.
I to the world am like a drop of water
That in the ocean seeks another drop,
Who, falling there to find his fellow forth,
Unseen, inquisitive, confounds himself:
So I, to find a mother and a brother,
In quest of them, unhappy, lose myself.

Enter Dromio of Ephesus

ANTIPHOLUS OF SYRACUSE:

Here comes the almanac of my true date. What now? How chance thou art returned so soon?

DROMIO OF EPHEBUS:

Returned so soon? Rather approached too late."

(I, ii)

Shakespeare adapts the *lazzo* once more in that Dromio and Antipholus are not lovers, but rather master/servant. He complicates the stage business beyond the simple use of characters coming on and off stage by the use of the two sets of twins. This enables Shakespeare to have the characters miss

each other whilst being mixed up as to their identity at the same time, an adaptation of the *commedia dell'arte* technique which adds to the madcap nature of the play.

Finally, it is useful to consider the twins as a way of bringing these points of analysis together – their use in the play addresses the stage business, characterisation, plot and theme. There are also *lazzi* that relate specifically to the use of twins. One of these is the “Lazzo of the Good/Bad Son. Not knowing that there are identical twins in the city, characters constantly mistake the good twin with the bad and vice versa” (Gordon, 2001, p.42). This is a fundamental aspect of the drive of the plot of *The Comedy of Errors* and is seen most in the confusion of Adriana, Antipholus of Ephesus’s wife. Antipholus of Ephesus is very different compared to his brother, Antipholus of Syracuse, who comes from a different background: Antipholus of Ephesus beats Dromio of Ephesus often when he does not listen and it is Dromio of Syracuse who mistakes Antipholus of Ephesus as his master. Antipholus of Ephesus also often cheats on Adriana with a courtesan who has promised money and gifts to:

Courtezan: Now, out of doubt Antipholus is mad,
Else would he never so demean himself.
A ring he hath of mine worth forty ducats,
And for the same he promised me a chain:
Both one and other he denies me now.
The reason that I gather he is mad,
Besides this present instance of his rage,
Is a mad tale he told to-day at dinner,
Of his own doors being shut against his entrance.
Belike his wife, acquainted with his fits,
On purpose shut the doors against his way.
My way is now to hie home to his house,
And tell his wife that, being lunatic,
He rush'd into my house and took perforce
My ring away. This course I fittest choose;
For forty ducats is too much to lose.

(IV, iii)

Antipholus of Syracuse, however, could be seen as the ‘Good Son’ and his less aggressive behaviour, which confuses Adriana when she spends time with him during the play. As Gilvary has pointed out, the other set of Antipholus of Syracuse and Dromio of Syracuse do not have the same morals as their ‘Bad’ counterparts seeing them as “loyal and trustworthy” (2004, p.9) in comparison to their twins.

A Midsummer Night's Dream

A Midsummer Night's Dream was written roughly a year after *The Comedy of Errors* (1594) as “the writing and performance of *A Midsummer Night's Dream* plausibly falls within the 1595-96 period” (Hunt, 2000, p.446) and represents another text in which the traces of *commedia dell'arte* can be unearthed. My exploration in this section of the chapter will draw focus towards the parallels and connections between the Lover characters in *commedia dell'arte* and Helena, Hermia, Lysander and Demetrius within *A Midsummer Night's Dream*. As well as looking at these characterisations, I will also explore how *lazzi* are present in the transformation of Bottom and I speculate on how the magic-transformed versions of the lovers in the woods can be metamorphosed into *commedia dell'arte* stock characters to help bring out definition in characterisation.

Figure 4. The lovers. INNAMORATI. (Delphano, 2021)

The maskless characters in *commedia dell'arte* are the stock characters known as The Lovers or the First Actor and Actress. They do not wear masks in order to show the make-up that they wear, which “in fact becomes a mask enabling performers to play the role well into middle-age, or even beyond” (Rudlin, 1993, p.107). The Lover characters were created from the context of “the Italian Renaissance courts [who] amused themselves with a form called *commedia erudita*” (Rudlin, 1993, p.106) and which then became essential to the plotlines delivered within *commedia dell'arte* performances. The Lovers represent “vain, petulant, spoilt, full of doubt and have very little patience” (Rudlin, 1993, p.109) but they do represent positive qualities as well since “there is no viciousness in them [...] They represent the human potential for happiness.” (Rudlin, 1993, p.109). In this study, my exploration of *A Midsummer Night's Dream* in Chapter 1 considers the dramaturgical trace of these archetypes in Shakespeare’s writing but also the influence on the writing of characterisation and plot development.

The plot starts off with Hermia and Lysander running away into the nearby magical woods from urban Athens after the disapproval of Egeus, Hermia’s father, towards the relationship. Demetrius, who is also in love with Hermia follows them, before Helena, herself in love with Demetrius, follows too. Puck, a fairy servant, helps Oberon, the King of the Fairies, play a trick on his partner Titania which

goes very wrong and results in her falling in love with a transformed version of the actor, Bottom, who was rehearsing in the woods and becomes donkey-like. A mix up in love magic results in Demetrius and Lysander fighting over Helena leaving Hermia stranded. In the end, Oberon forces Puck to remedy his errors which he does, and the two sets of lovers get back together. Hermia and Lysander's and Helena and Demetrius' marriage is approved by Duke Theseus.

The use of transformation is one of the key themes in *A Midsummer Night's Dream* as the characters undertake immediate personality and physical transformation owing to the misuse of magic. In relation to *commedia dell'arte*, Bottom's character is transformed in a way which requires the use of a mask, because of his head turning into that of a donkey. In Folio 1 version of the script it "mistakenly delays Bottom's reentrance at line 97 but adds that he now has on "the Asse head," il recognized property of the company. Following Puck's exit at this line (he is absent for the rest of the scene)" (Hunter, 2002, p.9) whereas shown in the final version it has:

FLUTE

O,--As true as truest horse, that yet would
never tire.

Re-enter PUCK, and BOTTOM with an ass's head

BOTTOM

If I were fair, Thisby, I were only thine.

QUINCE

O monstrous! O strange! we are haunted. Pray,
masters! fly, masters! Help!

Exeunt QUINCE, SNUG, FLUTE, SNOUT, and STARVELING

(III, I)

In *commedia dell'arte* 'The use of stock characters in commedia requires the individual identities of masks to be discernable immediately" (Weber, 2015, p.1), making masks "a part of the character as well as a tool of the actor" (Chapman, 1990, p.19). The character of Bottom is transformed into an ass during a rehearsal of *Pyramus and Thisby* as shown in the passage above. On top of this potential nod to *commedia dell'arte* through the use of mask, there is a record of a *lazzo* similar to Bottom's transformation, this is the "Lazzo of the Ass" describe by Gordon as "Through magic, Pantalone is transformed into an ass. Zanni mounts him and feeds him leaves from a tree" (Gordon, 2001, p.11). The use of the mask is shown in The Globe's production in 2013 of *Midsummer Night's Dream* when Bottom played by Pearce Quigley wears a full donkey grey mask in III.i after being transformed by

Puck during rehearsals of the play of Pyramus and Thisby directed by Peter Quince. You cannot see his face but are aware its Bottom due to the costume that the actor Pearce wears in the production. (Archive, 2023) The similarities between Shakespeare's plays and the *lazzo* are very clear - magic is used to transform characters into donkeys. This is more evidence of Shakespeare's plays being a performance artefact, formed by a variety of influences, rather than a singular vision – whilst there is no historical information to confirm Shakespeare's presence at a *commedia dell'arte* performance, a textual parallel such as this is so vivid that the influence points towards the possibility.

The influences surrounding the performance conditions of the play become even more complex when transformation, or metamorphosis, is explored more deeply. Both *commedia dell'arte* and Shakespeare may have been inspired by the Roman poet, Ovid's *The Metamorphoses* poems that were written around A.D. 2 to A.D. 8. Many of the titles in the book reference transformation such as "Jupiter transforms Io to a heifer" and "Acoetes's ship and crew are transformed". Bottom's own transformation has been described by Lucking as "a deliberately sardonic reminiscence of Ovid's *Metamorphoses* that presents a suggestive parallel to that undergone by Bottom" (Lucking, 2011, p.140). Shakespeare's text, therefore, has a combination of mainland European influences at its core – both a Roman poet and the performance traditions of *commedia dell'arte*, which are themselves influenced in part by Ovid, too.

The subplot involving 'the mechanicals' rehearsing play brings together several aspects of how transformation as a theme speaks to the performance codes of *commedia dell'arte*. In their retelling of the story of Pyramus and Thisby, the mechanical actors play different people in the play itself such as a Lion played by Snug. They do, in this sense, transform themselves into other people on stage – Shakespeare himself chooses to stage this transformation. These metamorphoses involve changes in gender, Flute, for example, who plays Thisbe; animals (the aforementioned Snug), objects; with Snout playing the wall that separates Pyramus and Thisby, and celestial bodies; with Starveling playing the moon. As a comic device, Shakespeare is taking a key element from Ovid and *commedia dell'arte* and following these to their absurd extreme – a character playing a wall being the clear case of this:

Wall

In this same interlude it doth befall
That I, one Snout by name, present a wall;
And such a wall, as I would have you think,
That had in it a crannied hole or chink,
Through which the lovers, Pyramus and Thisby,
Did whisper often very secretly.
This loam, this rough-cast and this stone doth show
That I am that same wall; the truth is so:

And this the cranny is, right and sinister,
Through which the fearful lovers are to whisper.

(V.i)

In contemporary performance, this moment in the play is often found amusing owing to its absurdity – something the spectators of the play-within-a-play also pick up on:

THESEUS

Would you desire lime and hair to speak better?

DEMETRIUS

It is the wittiest partition that ever I heard discourse, my lord.

(V.i)

In the *commedia dell'arte* influence performance conditions surrounding the creation of the text, it affords the actor playing Snout the opportunity to improvise and find his own *lazzo* in the moment. These transformations require the use of literal but also metaphorical masks and Shakespeare is creating his own cast of stock characters that make sense within the world of the play. This raises the possibility that he was poking fun at the Italian theatre form as well as the theme of transformation.

Outside of the mechanicals' subplot, traces of *commedia dell'arte* can be found within the choice of characterisation but also how they interact with magic and transformation. The unmasked Lover characters in *commedia dell'arte* can be found in figures such as Fedelindo "Lover. Son of Tartgalia" and Leilo "Lover. Leading young man" (Gordon, 2001, p.63). Parallels can be drawn between them and Lysander and Demetrius as well as with Helena and Hermia, who connect to *commedia dell'arte* characters such as Filesa "Lover. A young Spanish woman." and Cinzio "Female lover" (Gordon, 2001, p.61).

Puck's magic is mainly used with the lover stock characters and this speaks to two key themes of *commedia dell'arte* – mistaken identity (as explored above in relation to *The Comedy of Errors*) and transformation (as explored most recently). The key section of the play in relation to this is Hermia, Helena, Demetrius and Lysander's plotline when Puck puts a flower love potion in Lysander's eyes in II.ii believing him to be Demetrius. This potion causes whoever has it on their eyes to fall in love with the next person that they see. Lysander, in love with Hermia, wakes up and sees Helena, and the comic drive of this plot begins, as shown below:

LYSANDER

[Awaking] And run through fire I will for thy sweet sake.
Transparent Helena! Nature shows art,

That through thy bosom makes me see thy heart.
Where is Demetrius? O, how fit a word
Is that vile name to perish on my sword!

HELENA

Do not say so, Lysander; say not so
What though he love your Hermia? Lord, what though?
Yet Hermia still loves you: then be content.

LYSANDER

Content with Hermia! No; I do repent
The tedious minutes I with her have spent.
Not Hermia but Helena I love:
Who will not change a raven for a dove?
The will of man is by his reason sway'd;
And reason says you are the worthier maid.”

(II, ii)

On stage, there is much potential for the kinds of physical comedy typical of *commedia dell'arte* explored in a variety of ways in this thesis thus far. From a *commedia* perspective, you could have Lysander trying to touch Helena which Helena backs away from him frightened of what is happening to her with the change of recent events. She could slap him or pull away, but Lysander does not end his pursuit which makes Helena run away from him where Lysander doesn't stop. In this way it is a re-contextualisation of some of the stage language of Dromio found within *The Comedy of Errors*. The character of Helena becomes confused about Lysander's love interest changing from Hermia to herself causing Demetrius to fight over her.

Puck's mistake results in the four characters duelling over these mixed-up directions of pursuit – which causes Helena to emotionally breakdown about the new situation that she is unable to deal with – these emotions being overly explored in a way which links to common tropes of the Lovers in *commedia dell'arte*. There are also connections within the status of the characters and their connections to each other. Oberon is a master whilst Puck is his servant – this opens up possibilities of Oberon beating Puck in a slapstick manner when he discovers the mistake in III.ii:

OBERON

What hast thou done? thou hast mistaken quite
And laid the love-juice on some true-love's sight:

Of thy misprision must perforce ensue
Some true love turn'd and not a false turn'd true.

PUCK

Then fate o'er-rules, that, one man holding troth,
A million fail, confounding oath on oath.

OBERON

About the wood go swifter than the wind,
And Helena of Athens look thou find:
All fancy-sick she is and pale of cheer,
With sighs of love, that costs the fresh blood dear:
By some illusion see thou bring her here:
I'll charm his eyes against she do appear.

PUCK

I go, I go; look how I go,
Swifter than arrow from the Tartar's bow.

(III, II)

Through this reading, Puck's role is that of a Zanni figure and Oberon a Magnifico figure as he is the king of the fairies – although this situation is more fantastical than the urban comedy of *The Comedy Errors* the stage language is the same. Beyond the Zanni/Magnifico combination there are other readings of the characters, and their interactions with each other in terms of *commedia dell'arte* traces. Oberon can be seen to have traits of the jealous and lustful figure of Pantalone when Titania falls in love with Bottom due to Puck's spell despite being with Oberon. He could get angry at Puck for upsetting his personal relationship.

To return to the four lovers, one could argue that the transformations found within them when under the effects of Puck's spell can result in a change in which archetype they speak to. Lysander's behaviour, for example, could briefly be read, not as a mask-less lover type but instead as a Pantalone figure. As Fava and Rudlin state, Pantalone is mainly driven by lust (Fava, Rudlin, 1993). This abrupt change in behaviour that such a transformation could create would help to drive the pace and comic stage business:

LYSANDER

Now she holds me not;
Now follow, if thou darest, to try whose right,
Of thine or mine, is most in Helena.

DEMETRIUS

Follow! nay, I'll go with thee, cheek by jole.

(III, ii)

The character of Pantalone is mainly an older character who misses his youth, he has the obsession with love in women – whereas Lysander is a younger lover character who represents the differences in generation in urban Athens. By transforming him into such a different archetype, the transformation – an important thematic element of the play – can be fully explored. Another choice that could be made is informed by some textual clues. He could, instead, become II Capitano since when Demetrius chases after him, he is referred to as a coward - a quality which II Capitano was famous for:

Re-enter DEMETRIUS

DEMETRIUS

Lysander! speak again:
Thou runaway, thou coward, art thou fled?
Speak! In some bush? Where dost thou hide thy head?

PUCK

Thou coward, art thou bragging to the stars,
Telling the bushes that thou look'st for wars,
And wilt not come? Come, recreant; come, thou child;
I'll whip thee with a rod: he is defiled
That draws a sword on thee.

DEMETRIUS

Yea, art thou there?

PUCK

Follow my voice: we'll try no manhood here.

Exeunt

(III, ii)

Figure 5. Il Capitano (Delphano, 2021)

Il Capitano's mask "satirizes military power (in the historical context and in reference to foreign oppression" (De Luca, 1983, p.10) which shows the rebellion of the Italians going against the series of war ranging from War of the League of Cambrai in 1508 to War of Siena which ended in 1559 that devastated the country. The characteristics of Il Capitano are that he "thinks that he is god's gift which is untrue as he believes he is handsome" (Fava, Rudlin, 1993). On stage whilst performing, Capitano comes across "arrogant, ambitious soldier who delights in displaying learning as well as valor" (De Luca, 1983, p.10). Capitano is known as a coward despite his military role in a normal commedia dell'arte scenario. Capitano is manic with love and when it does not go his way, he ends up going "to drown himself" (De Luca, 1983, p.10). These masculine archetypes can be traced within many of Shakespeare's comedies.

By discussing *A Midsummer Night's Dream* and *The Comedy of Errors* within the context of *commedia dell'arte* performance traditions one can imagine Shakespeare's writing as being a performance artefact, rather than a written script. This approach is enabled by both this chapter's exploration of the traces of *lazzi*, theme, plot and characterisation found within the textual blueprints but also the presence of *commedia dell'arte* in the performance conditions connections found in the previous chapter's exploration of the influence of *commedia dell'arte* on the compositions of Shakespeare's company. The impact and influence of the theatre style *commedia* are present during William Kempe's time with the company but, as my conclusion to this thesis will explore, Shakespeare inherited this approach from the people and the performance movements around him and this legacy remained even in the last play that he wrote himself, in the form of *The Tempest*.

CHAPTER 2

Will Kempe: Commedia dell'Arte's Influence on his Improvisation and its Impact on Shakespeare's Writing.

Will Kempe's relationship with *commedia dell'arte* is important to look at since he was both a prominent member of Lord Chamberlain's Men and a performer strongly influenced by the Italian theatre style with the use of improvisation that was used in his performances in and out of the company.

This chapter will explore how Shakespeare's writing evolved with the company as a whole and trace *commedia dell'arte* roots through Kempe's impact by identifying key textual passages that he would have delivered when present onstage by going off the text that Shakespeare had written for the players playing with the audience or stage presented before him but also the comic stylistic shift that occurred when absent, following his departure from the Lord Chamberlain's Men. This approach will therefore focus on both close reading and a biographical exploration of Kempe's career to address the material conditions of the creation of some of Shakespeare's plays.

This chapter will address how the presence of *commedia dell'arte* improvisation techniques in Kempe's performance style can be used as a lens to examine Kempe's biography as it pertains to his working relationship with Shakespeare and, moreover, explains the conflict that is considered to have happened between the comic actor and the playwright prior to Kempe's departure from the company. Shakespeare's writing developed, I argue, with *commedia dell'arte* via the presence and contribution – and, later, absence – of Kempe. This position, which draws focus on the contemporary performance and working conditions of when Shakespeare was writing side-by-side with the texts themselves, is predominately adopting a New Historicist approach. In order to deliver this analytical framework, I will draw on the existing work of established Shakespeare performance history scholars such as Wiles's *Shakespeare's Clown: Actor and Text in the Elizabethan Playhouse* (1989), Gurr's *The Shakespearean Stage 1574 – 1642*. (1992), Weimann's *Shakespeare and the Popular Tradition in the Theater: Studies in the Social Dimension of Dramatic Form and Function* (1978) and Thompson's *Clowns, fools and knaves: stages in the evolution of acting* (2008). To see how Shakespeare's writing developed with Kempe's presence in the company, I will focus on two key texts – *Titus Andronicus* (1594) and *Romeo and Juliet* (1595) – whilst his absence will be noted through readings of *Hamlet* (1600) and *Twelfth Night* (1599/1600). The texts will be examined to see where *commedia dell'arte* performance tropes such as the *lazzi* are presented and consider textual evidence for Kempe's onstage improvisation to make the case for how the comic actor helped to shape those plays through his clowning which he was known for in his career.

Kempe's Biography: Influences, Impact and Inheritors

The first evidence of Will Kempe the actor is that he was a servant to Robert Dudley, Earl of Leicester who was a patron of one of the Elizabethan acting companies. Kempe was described as “properly uncommonly large” (Thompson, 2008, p.411) compared to most people at that time. As Wiles explains, the Leicester players visited Ipswich, England in 1580 where they most likely first met Will Kempe when Kempe was working for Dudley. Kempe was spotted by the players after they had been paid for a performance as the evidence of payment was listed “carrying a letter to Mr Kempe’ – an invitation to come and performs, perhaps” (Wiles, 1987, p.31). In 1585, during the on-going tensions between England and Spain, Kempe utilised his physical comedy clowning techniques to increase the morale with the troops based in Leicester. Kempe was apart of a entourage which included fourteen other actors and twelve musicians “who all helped Leicester to reciprocate the lavish entertainment he received en route.” (Willes, 1987, p.31). Kempe also had experience of performing in Europe – he toured with the company in the Netherlands in 1585 and a separate payment of twelve pounds was listed to Kempe in the records from that company after the performance in the Hague (Wiles, 1987, p.31).

Kempe's comic performances led him to become one of the first known celebrities and more known clowns in the UK within the theatre sector during the Elizabethan era (Thompson, 2008, p.411). He himself was an inheritor of the comic tradition of the performer Richard Tarlton; Kempe according to Gurr, “claimed descent from Tarlton” (Gurr, 1992, p.89). Tarlton's influence can mostly been seen through Kempe's ballads in his jigs which he wrote and performed, which will be considered in more detail later in this chapter. Theatre was a nascent art form in England during this period and the comic traditions and forms were actively being developed and adapted; Tarlton was the first famous clown in the Elizabethan era, and he paved the way for clowns such as Kempe. Kempe himself enabled the comic inheritance of Robert Armin, who replaced him in Shakespeare's company and scholars such as Gurr (1992) and Wiles (1989) have traced the impact Tarlton had on the theatre world at this time for the future generation of clowns.

Tarlton became famous during the 1570 period and was known not just as a clown but also “a maker of plays and ballads, a drummer, tumbler and qualified Master of Fencing” (Gurr, 1992, p.86). Tarlton was known for his wit as a comedian and his direct relationship with the audience – a key trait that Kempe inherited in his solo performances that he rose to fame with. There is clear evidence of Tarlton's use of improvisation to connect directly with audience as Stone highlights “Tarlton's reputed response to a woman who heckled from the audience, threatening to cuff him. Apparently, he agreed if she would reverse the spelling” (Stone, 2011, p.4).

Kempe directly inherited Tarlton's mantle when he joined Strange's Men in 1590 after the death of Tarlton as the company were looking for a ‘new folk hero’ which Kempe added to the role he played

with his famous jigs such as *Rowland*.² As well as performing, Kempe also wrote these jigs which were “short, comic, and often bawdy dialogue in song, sometimes featuring dance, slapstick, and disguise” (Clegg, 2016, p.302). Kempe did dances that were accompanied by a musician on stage whilst performing shows Tarlton’s influence on Kempe’s jigs. (Gurr, 1992, p.88). Warne (2020) describes Kempe’s jig as a short comic drama which was performed at the end of the play; these jigs became extremely popular and continued into Kempe’s work with the Lord Chamberlain’s Men and would have, therefore, also be performed after the delivery of Shakespeare’s plays (p.115). The popularity of Kempe’s routines such as in *A Knack to Know A Knave* (1592) can be traced since the title page of the written play had Kempe’s name on it to encourage readers to buy his play. The history of Strange’s Men company compared to Lord Chamberlain’s Men company history is hard to compare on Kempe’s impact within the two companies. The reason is the lack of evidence in Strange’s Men as there is not much historical analysis or research done with them. Meaning as scholarly researchers, it cannot be claimed if Kempe did make an impact in Strange’s Men compared Lord Chamberlain Men.

It is likely that Kempe met Shakespeare whilst working for the Strange’s Men since they performed alongside each other “for a performance at court – a fact which indicates that these three were the pivotal members of the new company” (Wiles, 1987, p.34). Kempe’s connection with Shakespeare became a turning point in his career as he had not had a stable period of work before the transition into the Lord Chamberlain’s Men. Kempe’s relationship with the audience was strong as audiences would come to see only him in Lord Chamberlain Men rather than Shakespeare’s plays itself due to the ‘clowning’ and was able to “interact with the audience so long as the playwright lacked his proper status of ‘poet’” (Wiles, 1987, p.35). As Kempe was changing Shakespeare’s work in each performance from his original work which is known today. This new working relationship did not signal a major change in Kempe’s style of performance, according to Wiles, since, “The clown was allowed the freedom of the stage, freedom for improvisation, rhyming and dancing” (Wiles, 1987, p.43).

This progress of improvisation with the work used in Kempe’s biography helps to highlight an evolution in comic acting on the Elizabethan stage; whilst Tarlton’s fame was very much a solo concern, more in line with 21st century stand-up comedians, A useful scholarly device needs to be done to understand the crucial differences of performers between Kempe and his replacement Armin. When Kempe departed the company, Robert Armin took over. Armin is mainly known to scholars as an author in his own right rather than a solo improvisatory comedian (Henze, 2013, p.419). Whilst there were aspects of similarity between Kempe and Armin in terms of performance style, Armin’s characters were mostly presented as fools (Gurr, 1992, p.88). In Elizabethan terms rather than modern terms, a fool is “who acts the fool’s part and the born or natural fool” (Wiles, 1987, p.5). Wiles

² Rowland’s jig is one of the last surviving texts from Kempe’s jig on record. According to Ford (2013) it intituled the character of Rowland soone in the jig. (p.69)

reasoning here is showcasing that Armin was a comedic performer which audiences loved. There would be recognisable signifiers for a person playing (or being) a fool since they would wear a suit of many colours (motley) and carried his props such as a dagger. In *King Lear* (1605), a play written after Kempe had left the company, a character is called The Fool and would have most likely been played by Armin in the King's Men (as the Lord Chamberlain's Men became known after the death of Elizabethan I in 1603). This fool figure, which Armin popularised, is different to the clown of Tarlton and Kempe who were known for being "powerful and popular performers who were authors and celebrities in their own right" (Stone, 2011, p.1). Clowns, such as the parts that Kempe played, are known for adding to, cutting, or changing the script, as well as undertaking the audience exchanges, whereas Armin's roles, such as The Fool, differed in this respect featuring more songs and intellectual humour between characters on stage such as in *Twelfth Night*.

Armin took over from Kempe's role within the company when Kempe left Lord Chamberlain's Men around 1599. The exact moment of Armin's arrival is disputed; Friedman (2022) argues against Wiles' statement saying Robert Armin did not join the company until August 1600 when he was listed in a Stationers Register 'at this houre [...] at the Globe on the Bankside men may see him" (p.4). The evolution of comic acting on the Elizabethan stage can therefore be traced from a solo clowning art form in Tarlton, to the application of this clowning within plays with Kempe such as in *Romeo and Juliet*, to the portrayal of fools on stage by Armin. Reflecting to Kempe, Wiles (1987) mentions that the scholars who study Shakespeare may know Kempe under 'Master Kemp' but William Kempe preferred to be called Will Kempe (p.24). This is an interesting development as Kempe is not stated to be a master, as a master is someone who has servants which Kempe never had since he was a servant himself. This is in keeping with the characters he played, which tended to be lower class roles. In the 'clowning' he was famous for that was used in the solo performances such as *Nine Days' Wonder* in which he Morris Danced from London to Norwich over a nine day period after he left the Lord Chamberlain's Men. Feats such as this helped Kempe arguably rise to greater fame, during his lifetime at least, over Shakespeare. Like *commedia dell'arte* performers, Kempe was an improviser who used his clowning talents to his advantage on stage, drawing on physical comedy. This improvisation arguably helped to build a lasting connection with audiences, but made his working relationships with playwrights such as Shakespeare difficult.

Having traced Kempe's position within the comic lineage of Elizabethan Theatre it is important, within the context of this thesis, to state his European credentials as a performer and, therefore expose the presence of *commedia dell'arte* in his acting DNA. Kempe did not stay in the Netherlands for a long period of time during his aforementioned visit in 1594 owing to wartime instability. Kempe's comic talents were used during this time to try and make Denmark join the English side of the military campaign. As Wiles states '[The Earl of] Leicester was keen at this juncture to woo the King of Denmark as a military ally, so once again Kemp's talent was employed for diplomatic purposes.'

(Wiles, 1987, p.32). Kempe contacted the English musicians heading to Denmark with a routine as he needed a reason to get to Denmark by following orders, presumably issued by his master. Kempe went on a ship with five other English actors in 1586, two of whom also went on to join the Lord Chamberlain's Men: Thomas Pope and George Bryan. Within this group of actors, as mentioned by Wiles, Kempe's talents were described as being 'instrumentalist' (Wiles, 1987, p.33). Which shows Kempe was multi-talented as he used music in his performances to aid the portrayal of his characters in his solo performances. Kempe was a solo comedian who used his talents to his advantage on stage wither Shakespeare liked it or not when with the company. He could "play his instruments, to demonstrate his athletic English dancing, and to provide such as other forms of table-side entertainment" (Wiles, 1987, p.31). At this moment in his career, it is clear to see Kempe working with Tarlton's tradition as a clowning solo performer. Kempe's work outside the UK helped his non-verbal performance skills as the majority of the audiences would have mostly likely not understood English. This draws a close correlation to *commedia dell'arte*, where the performers of these troupes used their bodies and physicality to show who they were on stage as each stock character had different movements. Just like Kempe, the *commedia dell'arte* troupes did not speak the native language of the country when they visited England briefly whilst they were based in France (Costola, 2012). In terms of folk performance stated at the beginning of the thesis, it can be said it was in tradition was used in *commedia* with the performances used in Italy and across Europe at the time.

At the end of Kempe's acting career, the parallels and traces of *commedia dell'arte* become potentially more concrete. According to Wiles, Kempe travelled to Italy around 1601 to prepare with an 'Italian Harlequin' who was performing *commedia dell'arte* in Paris, France when Italian troupes were performing for Louis XIV during that period. Kempe worked with the actor playing the character Arlecchino, the servant stock character in *commedia* (Wiles, p.36, 1987). Whilst this is clear evidence that Kempe was directly influenced by *commedia dell'arte* after his career in England, this information also highlights how *commedia* was part of the performance landscape in Early Modern theatre to the degree that a leading comic actor in England would travel abroad to learn more about this approach. Not enough is known about Kempe's early travels as a performer in Europe to be able to entirely rule out time spent with *commedia dell'arte* performers or companies but the biography of Kempe, alongside the close reading of performance texts which I will go on to undertake in the latter part of this chapter, adds to the body of evidence that the Italian theatre form was a key factor in the creation of Shakespeare's plays. Improvisation, a key facet of the form, was a major part of Kempe's skills as a performer and the developing influence of this aspect on Shakespeare's writing will be explored in depth below.

Kempe and Shakespeare: Improviser vs Writer

As stated above, a fundamental part of Kempe's acting approach, rooted in the legacies of Richard Tarlton, was improvisation – itself a key component of *commedia dell'arte*. It is interesting to reflect on how Kempe's continued improvisational interventions may have in fact shaped Shakespeare's own writing. For example, the role of 'Clown' in *Titus Andronicus*, likely written for Kempe, is introduced with the following with a stage direction in Act 4, Scene 3: “Enter a Clown, with a basket, and two pigeons in it” (IV, iii). Despite Kempe's growing reputation, it is likely this role was created for him to perform despite it being a small part with only twelve lines and being in two scenes in the whole play. It is the absence of written material for Kempe to deliver that indicate the part was written for him – by under writing the part, Shakespeare can be seen to be giving Kempe space to make the most out of his clowning abilities, rooted in improvisation.

The fact that the clown enters with unique props, such as pigeons, also gives Kempe the opportunity to create physical business – the links between this and *commedia dell'arte lazzi* will be explored later in the chapter. Shakespeare 'unwrote' Kempe's part to give him time to play with the text, the place around him, and establish the connection with the audience which was fundamental to the comic acting style. The Clown role in *Titus Andronicus* is one example of textual evidence of Kempe potentially breaking free from the script and improvising. The 'underwriting' of the part being one area where the conditions of original performance – i.e. the makeup of the theatre company – influences the creation of the text with *commedia dell-arte* influences in the form of the comic acting style of Will Kempe. There is, however, a field of study which suggests that this could have caused friction in the working relationship Shakespeare and Kempe had with each other.

The conflict between Kempe and Shakespeare appears to have come to a head sometime in the late 1590 during their time with the Lord Chamberlain's Men, although, it is unknown how bad it got. Kempe left the company around 1599 after this potential conflict arose. In the records from the Lord Chamberlain's Men, Kempe had a fifth of a share in The Globe theatre from February that year that would have been taken away from Kempe when departing the company in 1599. On February 21, 1599, “Kemp with his fellow-sharers of the Chamber-lain's company had signed the lease for the Globe” (Gray, 1930, p.7). Again, Kempe's presence – or in this case, absence – is reflected in Shakespeare's writing. For example, in *Julius Caesar*, there was no obvious clown part that Shakespeare had written which was performed in September 1599 or in *Henry V* in 1600 following Kempe's departure from the company. Prior to this, like in *Julius Caesar*, Kempe's “occupancy of the stage during the performance proper was less” (Gurr, 1992, p.89). This reduction in stage time could have angered Kempe, a man with a significant reputation as a performer, since he could not perform as much as he wanted to. Thomas Platter, a Swiss traveller, documented his experiences as an audience member of Lord Chamberlain Men's production of *Julius Caesar* in 1599. Friedman recounts how “Platter witnessed four actors ‘dance what was probably the jig’. Since the company had no other clown at that time, ‘One of those Globe dancers was most probably Kemp’” (2022, p.5)

which shows that Kempe either did indeed go against the *Julius Caesar* script that Shakespeare had written before his departure from the company.

In terms of another 1599 play, *Henry V*, it has been suggested that Kempe was meant to reprise Falstaff in *Henry V*, a role he had previously played in *Henry IV*. The relationship with Kempe and Shakespeare might have been falling apart at this stage which caused Shakespeare to rewrite the play and kill off Falstaff in the production – a potential cause for Kempe to leave the company completely around early 1600. He was meant to play Welsh Captain Fluellen if he did not leave the company. Scholars assume that ‘Kemp left the Chamberlain’s Men around the time that the Globe was being built in 1599 and did not take a role in either Henry V’ (Friedman, 2022, p.2). Kempe had sold his share in The Globe in 1599 before leaving despite being in the company till 1600.

Gurr (1992) also speculates that Kempe left due “having a hand in the piracy of the last Falstaff play, *The Merry Wives of Windsor*” (p.88). Wiles believes that scholars “reasonably seek the explanation for this sudden departure in professional differences” (1987, p.36), the implication being that Shakespeare possibly had lost patience with Kempe’s antics on stage improvising at the end of his plays or during a scene. As M.C. Bradbrook suggests, the improvisation that Kempe used “could ‘kill’ a scene to have the clown extemporising with the audience” (Stone, 2011, p.2). Despite scholars like Gurr and Wiles speculations, there is no definite evidence that can be conclusively used to determine why Kempe left the Lord Chamberlain’s Men. Sharpo suggests that Shakespeare had to remove Kempe from the company to develop a new direction for his company by creating a writer’s theatre which was against Kempe’s protocol in acting (Stone, 2011, p.2).

As stated in the early stages of this chapter, Kempe used his physicality and appearance to cause the audience to laugh with him. Upon leaving the company, he continued to perform in this way, most notably, “for his nine-day dance from London to Norwich in February 1600” (Thompson, 2008, p.411) where he toured *Nine Days of Wonder* across England from Norwich to London performing the same Morris dance. Although, Dyce (2007) argues that end of *Nine Days of Wonder* or *Nine Daies of Wonder* known to scholars “no record of this second feat has come down to us, we may conclude that it was never accomplished” (n.p) as it is speculated that Kempe died before the show was completed. Steele (1979) adds that the performance caused Kempe to refer to Shakespeare as a ‘penny poet’ after Kempe’s departure and believed Shakespeare stole the plot of *Macbeth* which was mentioned in Kempe’s performance of *Nine Days Wonder* (p.215). The acrimony appeared to be two sided with Shakespeare making a potential criticism of Kempe in *Hamlet*. At the start of the monologue performed by *Hamlet* to the players, Shakespeare references the improvisation that Kempe did whilst performing on stage. Hamlet specifically speaks about clowns more in Act 3, Scene 2, and insists that ‘clowns’ speak only their scripted lines:

HAMLET

O, reform it altogether. And let those that play
your clowns speak no more than is set down for them;
for there be of them that will themselves laugh, to
set on some quantity of barren spectators to laugh
too; though, in the mean time, some necessary
question of the play be then to be considered:
that's villanous, and shows a most pitiful ambition
in the fool that uses it. Go, make you ready.”(III, ii)

As Gurr (1992) states, Kempe “is rightly or wrongly thought to have been the culprit charged by Hamlet with speaking more than was set down for him” (p.88). As previously noted, it is around the time *Hamlet* was first performed that Robert Armin had taken over from Kempe’s role as a clown with Armin’s different performance style becoming the dominant comic driver with his fool characters.

Whilst exploring the biography of Kempe as a comic performer and improviser highlights the traces of *commedia dell’arte* in Shakespeare’s working methods, further evidence can be considered when analysing the structures of the text in two plays featuring Kempe and his comic inheritor, Robert Armin. In *Titus Andronicus*, Kempe played a minor role of the Lord Chamberlain’s Men, by contrast, Armin’s role as Feste in *Twelfth Night* is much more fully written, appearing across the whole play, which had 306 lines in *Twelfth Night* compared to Kempe’s role which has 23 lines in the two scenes in *Titus Andronicus*.

In terms of the texts themselves, the comparison below highlights the differences in humour that the characters deploy demonstrating the varying performance styles of the two comic actors:

<i>Titus Andronicus</i>	<i>Twelfth Night</i>
Clown played by Will Kempe	Feste played by Robert Armin
<p>TITUS ANDRONICUS</p> <p>But what says Jupiter, I ask thee?</p> <p>Clown</p> <p>Alas, sir, I know not Jupiter; I never drank with him in all my life.</p> <p>(I, iii)</p>	<p>FESTE</p> <p>Wit, an't be thy will, put me into good fooling!</p> <p>Those wits, that think they have thee, do very oft prove fools; and I, that am sure I lack thee, may pass for a wise man: for what says Quinapalus?</p> <p>'Better a witty fool, than a foolish wit.'”</p> <p>(I, v)</p>

In *Twelfth Night*, Feste, the part that Armin played, was witty and intelligent compared to what Kempe’s roles were in the company. As explained earlier, Armin was a writer as well as a performer

and his passage includes a quotation from Quinapalus, a name defined by Crystal and Crystal as ‘an (imagined) authority’ (Crystal, Crystal, 2024, n.p). The clown character in Titus, however, is highlighting their lack of intelligence, failing to understand who Jupiter is and turning this mistake into a drinking joke. There is also the possibility that, in the *Twelfth Night* passage above, by Feste saying ‘Better a witty fool, than a foolish wit.’ (I, V) Shakespeare is calling Robert Armin a ‘witty fool’ as he followed the script that Shakespeare gave to him, compared to Kempe who was ‘foolish wit’ as he did not tell Shakespeare what he was going to do each night but was undeniably popular with audiences.

Kempe: Conditioned by *commedia dell’arte*

The only specific biographical evidence of Kempe’s exposure to *commedia dell’arte* has been mentioned earlier in the chapter with his visit to Italy, after he left The Lord Chamberlain’s Men. This, however, does not mean that the influence of this theatre form began then. As a cultural materialist approach enables, Kempe’s influences as a performer were a result of the conditions in which he worked and these conditions were themselves a product of a variety of European performance traditions which directly and indirectly influenced the colleagues that Kempe worked with or watched. The comparison between Shakespeare and *commedia* should not be disregarded with the history of the two popular theatre styles due to the “changing elements of tradition and innovation [which] can be established and viewed as part of a more basic understanding of the theater” with social elements in Shakespeare’s and *commedia*’s work (Weimann, 1978, p.6). In this section of the chapter, therefore, I will use close reading, alongside an acknowledgement of the performing conditions of Early Modern London to bring to the surface the traces of *commedia dell’arte* in Kempe’s performances within Shakespeare’s texts but also contained in the jigs which established Kempe’s reputation as a comic performer.

Wiles believed that a clown like Kempe “performed not so much *for* an audience as with a community of spectators” (Wiles, 1987, p.102) as the clown in and outside of his scripted roles retains the intimate contact with the audience and stays with the community of the audience. As the previously explored performing history of Kempe has established, he was known for his ‘clown’ characters who would often improvise, dance and sing in plays but also in jigs written to be performed after the main play. Kempe’s jigs were often short but showed his comedic acting style whilst speaking and performed with music with a musician.

Kempe’s jig *Rowland* connects closely to the strong theme of ‘adulterating’ contained in *commedia dell’arte* scenarios. In the jig, this takes place with sexual innuendos between the servant John and his master’s wife who is not in a relationship with him. The master dresses up as the wife and a love triangle happens whilst the husband, dressed as a woman, sings his love for a servant (Wiles, 1987, p.51). In the original version, the plot is simple. The character of Rowland acts dead when his partner

Peggy leaves him for another man. Peggy becomes upset but decides to marry another man. Upon discovery of Rowland's plot, Peggy declares her love to him. The jig has four performers: two dancers who dance opposite from each other, whilst the other two are in the back or aside from the two main dancers. The main comic drive of the jig is the running commentary of what has just happened that the character of Rowland shares with the audience as so that they can see what is happening from his point of view (Wiles, 1987, p.50).

Firstly, from a *commedia dell'arte* perspective, one can see the young lover stock characters such as 'Celia. Lover. The love of the Captain and Doctor' and 'Cinthio. Lover. One of Arlecchino's male masters' (Gordon, 2001, p.61). Kempe updates these archetypes by re-casting them as more down-to-earth types, Peggy and Rowland, closer in social status to the audiences with which he was connected. Secondly, as the likely main performer in the jig, Kempe maintained his relationship with the audience throughout, narrating the action, even after the character's 'death'. The drive of the performance was comic, and the aim was to connect to the audience and get a response. This focus on comic skill and audience response is closely related to the performance tradition of *commedia dell'arte*.

The thematic and performance style traces of *commedia* in Kempe's own work and performances also found themselves in Shakespeare's plays. This can perhaps be seen most notably in *Romeo and Juliet* where Kempe is believed to have played Peter, the servant. Below I will make the case for the fact that Shakespeare included in his script a series of *lazzi* that could have come directly from Kempe's own improvised performances or, at the very least, performances that he was previously famous for. Before this exploration of Kempe in performance, it is necessary to undertake the argument that Kempe played Peter, or as he is sometimes listed Servant, in the play itself.

The evidence that Shakespeare wrote Peter for Kempe is shown in the quartos that were written in 1595. One of the lines in quarto one (Q1) has Kempe appear in an earlier scene as Capulet says on line 41 "Goe, goe choose dryer. Will will tell thee where thou shalt fetch them" (Ford, 2013, p.163). The first word of 'Will' that Capulet says is a possible reference to Kempe playing Peter in *Romeo and Juliet*. Scene 2 has a textual difference between the first and second quarto; the opening stage direction of the scene in Q1 has "'Enter Conntie Paris, old Capulet', followed twenty-seven lines later with 'Enter Seruingman'." Whilst the Q2 stage direction as "Enter Capulet, Countie Paris, and the Clowne" (Ford, 2013, p.164). The stage direction with the word 'Clowne' is a possible reference to Kempe entering the stage with the two other characters, which reveals what Shakespeare thought of Kempe at the time when writing him as Peter in *Romeo and Juliet*. In addition, Q2 appears to showcase Kempe's role bringing on a clown character at the start of the scene before the main plot needs him later as Peter. In Act 4, Scene 7 in the Q2 edition of the play a stage direction 'Enter Will Kempe' was in the edition before Peter got on stage (Ford, 2013, p.201).

A hint of Peter being written for Kempe is seen in the second quarto of *Romeo and Juliet* that was published in 1599. The second quarto evidence reveals two things “that Kemp played the part of Peter in early performances of the play; and second, that the ‘lamentations’ scene was adapted in some way in order to accommodate him, as most critics now suggest” (Ford, 2013, p.210). Shakespeare wrote that character with Kempe’s duties as a clown in mind in the repertory company. Kempe’s presence on stage was minor, however Kempe used those few scenes to his strengths to showcase his clown talents with Peter as shown in the argument scene with the two musicians. (Gurr, 1992, p.89). As I will argue below, Peter’s servant character was written for a sub-plot for the audience could experience comic relief from the main action that was happening on stage. These mostly manifested themselves as comedic *lazzi* that Kempe as Peter brought on stage such as the dispute scene with the two servants.

The final scene that features Peter in *Romeo and Juliet* contains a scenario that could be read as the “Lazzo of the Dispute” described by Gordon as “A common routine that resolves around an endless and frequently pointless argument between two or three characters” (Gordon, 2001, p.44). Within *Romeo and Juliet* the First and Second musician could be read as characters in the argument who demand payment to play music which Peter refuses. This *lazzi* causes the musicians to threaten violence on Peter for not listening to their request:

PETER

I will then give it you soundly.

First Musician

What will you give us?

PETER

No money, on my faith, but the gleek;

I will give you the minstrel.

First Musician

Then I will give you the serving-creature.

PETER

Then will I lay the serving-creature's dagger on

your pate. I will carry no crotchets: I'll re you,

I'll fa you; do you note me?

First Musician

An you re us and fa us, you note us.

Second Musician

Pray you, put up your dagger, and put out your wit.

(IV, v)

In the RSC's production of *Romeo and Juliet* from 2009, the actor Fergal McElherron, who plays Peter in the production, jumps up and down in the scene when saying 'I'll re you, I'll fa you. I'll sol you.' Getting ready to fight the musicians, he even goes to take off his jacket, with the musicians showing little interest. (Drama Online, n.d) As mentioned before in this chapter in relation to *Titus Andronicus*, Kempe would have implemented *commedia dell'arte* tactics using physical comedy with the use of props within the dispute that was happening on stage. In the case of *Romeo and Juliet* Peter may have grabbed one of the instruments that one of the musicians had to defend himself when they were suggesting that they will attack him, and he will not win the fight.

The biographical information explored earlier in this chapter can enable one to imagine this scene, on stage, with comic improvisations that Kempe could have delivered. Rather than viewing the text as 'fixed', it can be seen as a blueprint for comic business, much in the tradition of the *commedia dell'arte* scenario which only paint a fraction of performance picture that would have taken place. Perhaps Kempe and the two other actors could have developed the scene over the top like a military stand-off with the instruments as the weapons? As a renowned singer, dancer and musician, there is also the likelihood that Kempe could have broken into song whilst holding these instruments or danced from the sound of the instruments being wielded as weapons.

In the "Lazzo of Dispute" Gordon states that "each character will convince the other of the correctness of his views and the dispute will continued with the situation reversed" (Gordon, 2001, p.44). I argue that the dispute with Peter and the musicians was, from a plot perspective, pointless as the musicians were not ready to perform and Peter was impatient which caused a disagreement with the three characters over a song and a payment. Shakespeare could have written this, much like the clown scene in *Titus Andronicus*, to give the audience and a actors break from the main tragic plot between Romeo and Juliet. It is important, therefore, to acknowledge Kempe's comic function and influence as existing across the genres of Shakespeare's plays, not just his Comedies.

Another trace of *commedia dell'arte* in the character of Peter can be found in Kempe's possible use of improvisation of in relation to speaking misplaced words. These were common foundations for *lazzi*, in the case of I.ii in *Romeo and Juliet* this is the "Lazzo of the List [...] Everything is mispronounced. So, 'four chickens' becomes 'four broken pillards.' And so forth." (Gordon, 2001, p.58). In this scene the character listed as Servant receives a letter but cannot read or understand it as he has not learned to read. The servant ends up getting Romeo to read the letter that he cannot read later in the scene itself.

Servant

God gi' god-den. I pray, sir, can you read?

ROMEO

Ay, mine own fortune in my misery.

Servant

Perhaps you have learned it without book: but, I pray, can you read any thing you see?

ROMEO

Ay, if I know the letters and the language.

Servant

Ye say honestly: rest you merry!

ROMEO

Stay, fellow; I can read.

(I, ii)

Back when the play was first performed, Kempe could have improvised around this *lazzo* as a way of connecting more directly to his audience, the importance of which has been established earlier in this chapter. This is due to the fact that people struggled with literacy in 1500-1600 in exactly the same way which causes the servant to struggle in Shakespeare's writing above – it is considered that in the sixteenth century, literacy rates were between twenty and thirty percent amongst men and twenty per cent amongst women (Folger Shakespeare Library, 2020). On stage, Peter, the Servant character, has similar traits to the clown character from *Titus Andronicus* that Kempe played in that the part is 'under-written' with just 33 lines but has much potential for improvisation. With this point in mind, the stage direction written in the quarto which wrote Kempe's name, instead of a character's name, speaks to Kempe's popularity at the time.

Conclusions: Kempe's Small Parts but Bigger Presence

As shown with the evidence throughout this chapter, Will Kempe's connection with *commedia dell'arte* becomes apparent through his biography and his work with Lord Chamberlain's Men. This approach was enabled by treating Shakespeare's texts, in the spirit of Cultural Materialism, as one part of a broader performance landscape in Shakespeare's lifetime. The examples of text in *Titus Andronicus* and *Romeo and Juliet* are traces of this context and surrounding performance styles such as *commedia dell'arte* and show that these plays would not have been written in this way without Kempe and his influences and inheritors.

The small number of recorded lines that Kempe had for each character are not a sign of his small influence on the creation of these plays: Kempe did not have a small role in each production, his role was small but his presence on stage was significant. Piecing together when he left companies such as Lord Chamberlain's Men and Strange's Men helps our understanding on Kempe's biography in relation to the influence of comic acting traditions existent at the time from performers such as Richard Tarlton and *commedia dell'arte*. Kempe was a comedic international performer and, as a key part of The Lord Chamberlain's Men during the first half of Shakespeare's writing career, this means that Shakespeare's texts themselves are shifts the context of reception with the audience.

Having traced the influence of *commedia dell'arte* through the specific characters played by a *commedia* influenced performer such as Kempe in this chapter, I will now move on to unearth more connections by examining the presence of *lazzi* in some of Shakespeare's comedies. Like the examples considered in this chapter, I will treat these scripts as traces of broader performances, not created by one man but as a result of many influences and factors.

CONCLUSION

Shakespeare: an inheritor of *commedia dell'arte* to the last

A final conclusionary exploration is necessary to establish Shakespeare as an inheritor of *commedia dell'arte* as a theatre form. All four of the texts explored in detail in this thesis came from the period of Shakespeare's career when Will Kempe was a member of the company. A counter argument could, therefore, be made that it was the actors surrounding Shakespeare that had this direct influence on the creation of the text. As established earlier in this thesis, Kempe most likely left the Lord Chamberlain's Men in 1599 but, by addressing *The Tempest* (1611), Shakespeare's final single authored play, it is possible to see that the impact of *commedia dell'arte* remained.

There are several *lazzi* from *commedia* that deal directly with storms and shipwrecks. One such is the "Lazzo Of The Boy in the Tempest... Coviello meets the father of a boy who was in a shipwreck" (Gordon. 2001, p.19). Like Shakespeare's adaptations of *lazzi* explored earlier in *The Comedy of Errors*, the plot of *The Tempest* speaks to, but does not entirely copy, this *lazzo*. Whereas the *lazzo* involves the protagonist meeting the father of a boy who was in a shipwreck, Shakespeare adds extra layers to this encounter in his play. Prospero already knew the father (Alonso) of the boy (Ferdinand) in the shipwreck and this father also is involved in the wreck. A second *lazzo* in Gordon's study on *lazzi* could be seen to have been adapted by Shakespeare: "Lazzo of the Tempest Survived... Coviello describes a story of a ship in a tempest and how he was saved from it" (Gordon, 2001, p.26). Here, the analysis of *The Tempest* could take several angles. Is Alonso the Coviello figure? Someone who is 'saved' by the shipwreck by receiving forgiveness by Prospero at the end of the play for his role in Prospero's exile? Or is Prospero the Coviello figure, needing the shipwreck to be 'saved' from his exile on the island?

Beyond the thematic and plot-based traces of *commedia dell'arte*, the stage business of the theatre form can be seen in *lazzi* found within the 'gaberдинe scene' in II.ii. Trinculo, a shipwrecked jester, and Caliban, Prospero's servant/slave resident on the island, are hiding under the same cloth (or gaberдинe) from the oncoming thunder storm when Stephano, a shipwrecked butler who is friends with Trinculo, comes across the bodies under the gaberдинe which seems like a 'strange' object to him, probably owing to the large amount of alcohol he has drunk. His investigations into the object contain some rich potential connections to the stage language of *commedia dell'arte*:

CALIBAN

Do not torment me: Oh!

STEPHANO

What's the matter? Have we devils here? Do you put tricks upon's with savages and men of Ind, ha? I have not scaped drowning to be afeard now of your four legs; for it hath been said, As proper a man as ever went on four legs cannot make him give ground; and it shall be said so again while Stephano breathes at's nostrils.

CALIBAN

The spirit torments me; Oh!

STEPHANO

This is some monster of the isle with four legs, who hath got, as I take it, an ague. Where the devil should he learn our language? I will give him some relief, if it be but for that. if I can recover him and keep him tame and get to Naples with him, he's a present for any emperor that ever trod on neat's leather.

CALIBAN

Do not torment me, prithee; I'll bring my wood home faster.

(I, ii)

There are several opportunities for the original cast to improvise around this scenario and for contemporary performers to do the same. Caliban could struggle with flatulence owing to nerves at the new residents of the island, or even his diet which could be established earlier in the play. As

Stephano examines the 'object' which he sees, 'Have we devils here?' this flatulence could be released. The 'flatulence' comes from one of the *lazzis* categories in *commedia*. "The Sexual/Scatological Lazzi, the so-called 'stage crudities' of *Commedia*, were among the most popular routines" (Gordon, 2001, p.32) as the 'flatulence' comes under scatological. The smell could have an impact on Stefano's ability to speak and move, and Trinculo could also react to this, being placed underneath the gaberdine himself. He could become very agitated and want to escape from the cloth – thus reinforcing the strangeness of the 'object' which Stefano is addressing. The idea can be seen in RSC's production of *The Tempest* in 2013. Trevor Fox plays Trinculo and James Gannon plays Caliban and the two chase each other under a cloth, panicking about what they believe they can see in front of them whilst Stefano, played by Sam Cox, describes the object he is seeing. (Drama Online, n.d) This scatological approach speaks directly to the traditions of *commedia dell'arte* – particularly the coarse humour that Zanni characters used, as documented in the Introduction to this thesis.

Another staging option could be to draw directly on the "Lazzo of Falling Asleep... As soon as Lelio drags him in, Arlecchino immediately falls asleep on the floor. Arlecchino stands and again falls asleep in Lelio's arms" (Gordon, 2001, p.12). In the extract highlighted above, Trinculo does not speak – this absence of lines could be justified by having him fall asleep. As Stephano examines the 'object', Trinculo could be brought up standing, and then fall down again – or arranged in increasingly ridiculous poses which always result in him falling back asleep. Both approaches could be combined if the effects of Caliban's flatulence could cause Trinculo to fall asleep or, pass out owing to the awful smell. These *lazzi* from *commedia dell'arte* were useable by the actors in the King's Men but it is poignant to consider that Will Kempe could have brought so much comic expertise to this scene, by this point his celebrity status in England had been lost and Kempe most likely had died of the plague in 1603 as the only source of his death stated 'it was getting dark, where my Will Kempe laid death-sick' (Weaver, 2006, p.9). This one source adds further sadness by suggesting Kempe died of an illness associated with poverty.

Findings and Future Research

The research journey contained within this thesis has aimed to connect *commedia dell'arte* and Shakespeare's plays in a way to further the research undertaken by scholars such as Kathleen Lea and Andrew Grewer. Due to the fact, that they began the research of the connections with *commedia* and Shakespeare's work in the 20th century. The work made by the scholars should not be disregarded and has not been disregarded as the research helped the thesis argument I have made. I believe the key to this contribution has been enabled by a methodology that unearths the traces of *commedia dell'arte* through a cultural materialist lens applied to close reading and a new historicist view of Will Kempe's career.

A key finding of this study has been locating the influence of *commedia dell'arte* beyond Shakespeare's comedies by exploring *Romeo to Juliet* when Kempe played Peter, and the Clown in *Titus Andronicus*. This has a double significance in that it demonstrates the importance of Kempe within the company – that even tragedies needed a moment for the company comedian to express himself – and, therefore, that the roots of the comic Italian performance style transcended the genres of Shakespeare's time. The *lazzi* are clear within the text, such as the 'Lazzo Of The Dispute' and the 'underwriting' of the role plays to Kempe's strength as an improviser.

Another finding has been my identification of the impact of *commedia dell'arte* in Shakespeare's plays through the traces of *lazzi* in both Chapter 1 and Chapter 2. This research could be expanded in a future study of all of Shakespeare's plays and the creation of a resource for theatre makers and researchers to be able to draw out more detail in the staging of these scenes through the presence of comic stage business influenced by *commedia dell'arte*. My research in this thesis has attempted, therefore, to imagine not only how the stage language of *commedia dell'arte* could have functioned in Shakespeare's time but also how this could continue to function in contemporary performance.

Reference List

- Archive (2023) *Midsummer's Night Dream*, 2013 Globe production. Available at: <https://archive.org/details/a-midsummer-nights-dream-2013> [Accessed 22nd April 2025]
- Baskervill, C.R. (1924) Mummers' wooing plays in England. *Modern Philology*, 21(3), pp.225-272. Available at: <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/pdf/10.1086/387500> [Accessed 2nd April 2025]
- Clegg, R. (2016) "A Ballad Intituled a Pleasant Newe Jigge": The Relationship between the Broadside Ballad and the Dramatic Jig. *huntington library quarterly*, 79(2), pp.301-322. Available at: https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/huntlibrquar.79.2.301.pdf?casa_token=O-kEC29uCyIAAAAA:VXQTcFDTLEHZgUomMDSBKaRsna8m5BkyGLwkSn7x1ZclI39cYP3WqYd2WwRKBDNKymtsWbbsSbyab5PFuwtQQhmyz5Vp56f68i3KPCUDzXwGxswOCaf5LA [Accessed 19th August 2024]
- Chiari, S. (2014). Upstart Crow vs. University Wit: Shakespeare "Beautified". In *Forum for World Literature Studies* (Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 140-159). Wuhan Guoyang Union Culture & Education Company. Available at: <https://www.fwls.org/uploads/soft/210603/10479-210603163058.pdf> [Accessed 28th April 2025]
- Chapman, L. A. (1990). *Masks: A Viable Option for the Modern Stage*. Lindenwood College. Available at: <https://digitalcommons.lindenwood.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1504&context=theses> [Accessed 13th May 2024]
- Costola, S. (2012) *AS2P Lazzi acrobazia cibo*. 3rd April. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VpIfWbFosD0> [Accessed 27th August 2024]
- Crick, O. (2022) (Re) evaluating improvisation in commedia dell'Arte, *Comedy Studies*, 13:2, 125-138. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/2040610X.2022.2091384> [Accessed 22nd January 2024]
- Crystal, D, Crystal, B. (2024) Characters by part sizes. Available at: <https://www.shakespeareswords.com/Public/Characters.aspx> [Accessed 5th December 2024]
- D'Anna, C. (2019) *A Journey Back Home Through a Mask for the 21st century: The Legacy of Commedia dell'Arte in Postdramatic Theatre with particular focus on the centrality of the actor in Devised Performance*. PhD Thesis. London Metropolitan University. Available at: http://repository.londonmet.ac.uk/5017/1/D%27Anna%2CChiara_PhD_001_Resubmission_May-2019.pdf [Accessed 19th January 2024]
- De Colle, S., Freeman, R. E., Parmar, B., & de Colle, L. (2017). Practicing human dignity: Ethical lessons from Commedia dell'Arte and Theater. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 144, 251-262. Available at:

https://idp.springer.com/authorize/casa?redirect_uri=https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10551-015-2898-4&casa_token=NijWlmQEtQIAAAAA:SNerNujS_CcTO9Ru4gPJ0uxMRMXezG1PYHSZgh6P2EuOkQkA_KJhI23RQhqPqAT9EwBAafgzfcjv1lc [Accessed 20th February 2024]

Delphano, R. (2021) The Captain | Il Capitano | Commedia dell'Arte | Maurice Sand illustration. [Photograph] Available at: <https://www.delpiano.com/carnival/html/captain.html> [Accessed 14 December 2024]

Delphano, R. (2021) Innamorati | Lovers | Commedia dell'Arte | Maurice Sand illustrations. [Photograph] Available at: <https://www.delpiano.com/carnival/html/innamorati.html> [Accessed 14 December 2024]

De Luca, A. (1983). Structural and thematic parallels between the 'Commedia dell'arte' and 'the theatre of the absurd'. University of Alberta. MA Thesis. Available at: <https://era.library.ualberta.ca/items/efff5f3-622b-4329-aac4-3ee026f1a3f2/download/1dae6a06-3a77-407b-af4a-e83f2003fd1e> [Accessed 16th October 2023]

Dickson, W, P, Becker, M. (2023) Did Jonson and Shakespeare Really Admire One Another? Shakespeare Oxford Newsletter, 59(3), p.12-16. Available at: <https://shakespeareoxfordfellowship.org/wp-content/uploads/SO-Newsletter-Summer-2023.pdf> [Accessed 28th April 2025]

Dollimore, Sinfield (ed) (1985) Political Shakespeare : new essays in cultural materialism. Manchester University Press. Available at: https://archive.org/details/politicalshakesp0000unse_b0z1/page/n3/mode/2up [Accessed 21st November 2024]

Drama Online (n.d) Romeo and Juliet, Globe on Screen, Shakespeare's Globe on Screen (2008-2015). Available at: https://www.dramaonlinelibrary.com/video?docid=do-9781350997233&tocid=do-9781350997233_6315564513112 [Accessed 14th April 2025]

Drama Online (n.d) The Comedy of Errors, Globe on Screen, Shakespeare's Globe on Screen (2008-2015). Available at: https://www.dramaonlinelibrary.com/video?docid=do-9781350997431&tocid=do-9781350997431_5278064928001 [Accessed 18th April 2025]

Drama Online (n.d) The Tempest, Globe on Screen, Shakespeare's Globe on Screen (2008-2015). Available at: https://www.dramaonlinelibrary.com/video?docid=do-9781350997547&tocid=do-9781350997547_4598376277001 [Accessed 18th April 2025]

Dyce, A. (2007) Kemps Nine Daies Wonder: Performed in a Daunce from London to Norwich. Available at: <https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/21984> [Accessed 9th May 2025]

- Eisner, M. (2013). *Boccaccio and the Invention of Italian Literature* (No. 87). Cambridge University Press. Available at:
https://www.academia.edu/download/32030193/Eisner_Boccaccio_and_the_Invention_of_Italian_Literature_Excerpt.pdf [Accessed 9th May 2024]
- Fava, A. Rudlin, J. (1993) MASKS OF THE COMMEDIA DELL'ARTE. Arts Archives (electronic edition) ISSN 0967 – 0416. Arts Documentation Unit, A Council of Europe initiated project. Exeter. UK. Dir: Peter Hulton. [Accessed 28th November 2023]
- Folger Shakespeare Library. (2020) Books and Reading in Shakespeare's England. *Shakespeare Unlimited*. Episode 137. Available at: <https://www.folger.edu/podcasts/shakespeare-unlimited/books-reading/> [Accessed 18th December 2024]
- Ford, E. (2013) Will Kemp, Shakespeare, and the Composition of "Romeo and Juliet". *Early Theatre*, 13(2), 162–175. Cardiff University. PhD Thesis. Available at:
<https://orca.cardiff.ac.uk/id/eprint/48023/1/EFordPhD2013.pdf> [Accessed 3rd November 2023]
- Frey, N, Fisher, D. (2013) What is Close Reading?. *Principal Leadership*. Available at:
<https://www.mdek12.org/sites/default/files/Offices/Secondary%20Ed/ELA/tools/close-reading-explained.pdf> [Accessed 8th May 2024]
- Friedman, M.D. (2022) 'I am but a fool, look you': Will Kemp and the Performance of Welshness. *Early Theatre: A Journal associated with the Records of Early English Drama*, 25(1), pp.57-77. Available at: <https://earlytheatre.org/earlytheatre/article/view/4411/4242> [Accessed 30th September 2024]
- Gilvary, K. (2004) Shakespeare and Italian Comedy. *Great Oxford: Essays on the Life and Work of Edward de Vere, 17th Earl of Oxford, 1550, 1604*, p.124. Available at: <https://deveresociety.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/KG-2004-ShakespeareItalianComedy.pdf> [Accessed 24th October 2023]
- Gordon, M (2001) *Lazzi. The Comic Routines of the Commedia dell'Arte*. Johns Hopkins University Press. [Accessed 5th October 2023]
- Gray, H. D. (1930). The Roles of William Kemp. *The Modern Language Review*, 261-273. Available at:
https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/3715765.pdf?casa_token=R0wJ5iFWp38AAAAA:088fDOJgg_qj1SB9nIhUjMTI7Wx4-zc_BeVc_8dNEpaaAaoqg769K4yMWKc72d-2Nkczf8OKDLPkSwbXROQHCZrZqEYAwOeKPFzV1w7cd8LWBdAFRieE [Accessed 4th December 2024]

Greenblatt, S. and Cohen, W. eds. (2015) *The Norton Shakespeare: Third International Student Edition*. WW Norton & Company. [Accessed 20th May 2024]

Gurr, A. (1992) *The Shakespearean Stage 1574 – 1642*. Third Edition. Cambridge University Press. [Accessed 10th November 2023]

Harris, Jonathan Gil (2003) "Materialist Criticisms." In *Shakespeare: An Oxford Guide*. Edited by Stanley Wells and Lena Cowen Orlin, 472–491. New York: Oxford University Press. Available at: [https://www.google.co.uk/books/edition/New_Historicism_and_Cultural_Materialism/d5FKEAAAOBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=Harris,+Jonathan+Gil+\(2003\)+%E2%80%9CMaterialist+Criticisms.%E2%80%9D+In+Shakespeare:+An+Oxford+Guide.+Edited+by+Stanley+Wells+and+Lena+Cowen+Orlin,+472%E2%80%93491.+New+York:+Oxford+University+Press.&printsec=frontcover](https://www.google.co.uk/books/edition/New_Historicism_and_Cultural_Materialism/d5FKEAAAOBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=Harris,+Jonathan+Gil+(2003)+%E2%80%9CMaterialist+Criticisms.%E2%80%9D+In+Shakespeare:+An+Oxford+Guide.+Edited+by+Stanley+Wells+and+Lena+Cowen+Orlin,+472%E2%80%93491.+New+York:+Oxford+University+Press.&printsec=frontcover) [Accessed 25th November 2024]

Henke, R. (2018) "England," in Balme, C. B., Vescovo, P., and Vianello, D. (eds) *Commedia dell'Arte in Context*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (Literature in Context), pp. 115–122. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/abs/commedia-dellarte-in-context/england/BDF4B053215EE93AE177E6455CD9AE0E> [Accessed 25th October 2023]

Henze, C.A., 2013. "Wise enough to play the fool": Robert Armin and Shakespeare's sung songs of scripted improvisation. *Comparative Drama*, 47(4), pp.419-449. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/24615297.pdf> [Accessed 25th September 2024]

Holderness, G. (1988) *The Shakespeare myth*. Manchester University Press. Available at: <https://archive.org/details/shakespearemyth0000unse/page/12/mode/2up> [Accessed 21st November 2024]

Hunt, M. (2000). A Speculative Political Allegory in *A Midsummer Night's Dream*. *Comparative Drama*, 34(4), 423-453. Available at: https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/41154056.pdf?casa_token=LhXbdHVQ5ykAAAAA:Ust3frsL6bxVjkRutNTah9I7YBH55Oj6sxNAz0EQ-C5pmilixlgXHLNQwrqvsXbOK63f6RNF1x_nHTJFrFC679jJeuAI2dpOrPtqG52LtKflEXpqjA [Accessed 11th December 2024]

Hunter, W. B. (2002). New Readings of *A Midsummer Night's Dream*. *ANQ: A Quarterly Journal of Short Articles, Notes and Reviews*, 15(4), 3-10. Available at: https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/08957690209600077?casa_token=PmOGYZjae24AAA:AA:Q9k3HGvGyZ69LTZNIR8_6RA1yC9A3J3qYmqg6QeoUyyIKWIMqfkAsG5mVeCsK1jUoYqbAyYWWxI [Accessed 11th December 2024]

- Lucking, D. (2011). Translation and Metamorphosis in *A Midsummer Night's Dream*. *Essays in criticism*, 61(2), 137-154. Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/eic/article-pdf/61/2/137/1245877/cgr002.pdf> [Accessed 26th January 2024]
- Moscatello, R. (n.d) Zanni, the smart servant. [Photograph] Available at: <https://riccardo.artstation.com/projects/A4Aye> [Accessed 13th February 2024]
- Naccari, F. (2014). Costume di Magnifico (della commedia dell'arte, bene complesso/ ins. *Cultura.gov.it*. [Photograph] Available at: <https://catalogo.cultura.gov.it/detail/DemoEthnoAnthropologicalHeritage/1201254199-0> [Accessed 14th Dec 2024]
- Parvini, N. (2017) *New Historicism*. Oxford Bibliographies. *Oxford University Press*. Available at: <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/display/document/obo-9780190221911/obo-9780190221911-0015.xml> [Accessed 8th May 2024]
- Pugliatti, P. (2016). 'ready apparrelled to begyn the play': Collaboration, Text and Authorship in Shakespeare's Theatre and on the Stage of the *Commedia dell'Arte*. *Journal of Early Modern Studies*, 5. Available at: <https://oajournals.fupress.net/index.php/bsfm-jems/article/download/7062/7060> [Accessed 25th October 2023]
- Royal Shakespeare Company (2017). Timeline of Shakespeare's plays | Royal Shakespeare Company. Available at: <https://www.rsc.org.uk/shakespeares-plays/histories-timeline/timeline> [Accessed 5th June 2024]
- Royce, A.P. (1986) 'The Venetian *Commedia*: Actors and Masques in the Development of the *Commedia dell'Arte*', *Theatre Survey*, 27(1–2), pp. 69–87. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0040557400008802> [Accessed 9th May 2024]
- Rudlin, J. (1994) *Commedia dell'Arte An Actors Handbook*. Routledge. [Accessed 14th November 2023]
- Sand, M. (2024) Costume and theatre character: Pantalone (doctor) draws from 'Masques et bouffons' (Italian comedy: *Commedia dell'arte*). [Photograph] MeisterDrucke. Available at: <https://www.meisterdrucke.uk/fine-art-prints/Maurice-Sand/948466/Costume-and-theatre-character%3A-Pantalone-%28doctor%29-draws-from-%27Masques-et-bouffons%27-%28Italian-comedy%3A-Commedia-dell%27arte%29.html> [Accessed 14 December 2024].
- Stone, A. (2011) "*Am I a Clowne?*": *Clowning in Shakespeare*. Masters dissertation, University of Otago. Available at: https://ourarchive.otago.ac.nz/view/pdfCoverPage?instCode=64OTAGO_INST&filePid=13397215980001891&download=true [Accessed 29th October 2024]

Schmitt, C, N. (2004) Commedia dell'Arte: characters, scenarios, and rhetoric, *Text and Performance Quarterly*, 24:1, 55-73. Available at:

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1046293042000239438> [Accessed 9th October 2023]

Schrickx, W. (1976). Commedia Dell'Arte Players in Antwerp in 1576: Drusiano and Tristano Martinelli. *Theater Research International* , 1 (2), 79-86. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0307883300000833> [Accessed 9th May 2024]

Shakespeare, W. (n.d) A Midsummer Night's Dream. Martsons Press. [Accessed 5th October 2023]

Shakespeare, W. (2008) The Comedy Of Errors. Edited by Whitworth, C. The Oxford Shakespeare. Oxford World Classics. [Accessed 20th October 2023]

Shakespeare, W. (n.d) Hamlet. Available at: <https://shakespeare.mit.edu/hamlet/full.html> [Accessed 21st August 2024]

Shakespeare, W. (n.d) Titus Andronicus. Available at:

<https://shakespeare.mit.edu/titus/full.html> [Accessed 21st August 2024]

Shakespeare, W. (n.d) Romeo and Juliet. Available at:

https://shakespeare.mit.edu/romeo_juliet/full.html [Accessed 13th August 2024]

Shakespeare, W. (n.d) The Tempest. Available at: <https://shakespeare.mit.edu/tempest/full.html> [Accessed 10th October 2023]

Shakespeare, W. (1998) Twelfth Night. The Arden Shakespeare. Second Edition. Edited by J.M.Loethian and T.W.Craik. Bloomsbury Publishing PLC. [Accessed 13th October 2023]

Smith, B. H. (2016). What was “close reading”? A century of method in literary studies. *The Minnesota Review*, 2016(87), p. 57-75. Available at: http://www.digitalhermeneutics.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/What_Was_Close_Reading_A_Century_of_Meth.pdf [Accessed 8th May 2024]

Steele, E. (1977). Shakespeare, Goldoni, and the Clowns. *Comparative Drama*, 11(3), 209-226. Available at:

https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/41152748.pdf?casa_token=gergxWVJfiUAAAAA:hVn5nRTdFXDUAREgEyPbwU31-OoJnQZDkHIGhg9HTkeRt7hRswXEDENKCr2laWvU4JdQIqtMb0DZVvzSthpbJ6uwl3q5iz6X-wkzJ-7AEJqT6QyIMqEug [Accessed 21st August 2024]

Steel, E. (2017). VERBAL COMIC GAGS IN SHAKESPEARE'S PLAYS FROM ADLIBBING ITALIAN COMEDIANS. *KARE*, 2(1), 29-36. Available at:

<https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/493378> [Accessed 20th February 2024]

Thompson, P. (2008) Clowns, fools and knaves: stages in the evolution of acting. [Accessed 25th July 2024]

Vickers, B. (2017) 'Upstart Crow'? The Myth of Shakespeare's Plagiarism, *The Review of English Studies*, Volume 68, Issue 284, April 2017, Pages 244–267. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/res/hgw093> [Accessed 28th April 2025]

Warne, A. (2020) Put on a Noddies Coate. PhD Thesis. University of Roehampton. Available at: https://pure.roehampton.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/3447993/Put_on_a_Noddies_Coate.pdf [Accessed 21st August 2024]

Weber, E.L. (2015). Commedia dell'Arte, Masks and Masking: A Modern Application for the Production of Commedia Masks. An Independent Research and Application Process. Kaleidoscope, 8(1), p.14. *University of Kentucky*. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/232567288.pdf> [Accessed 13th May 2024]

Weaver, G. (2006). The Death of Will Kempe. *The Sewanee Review*, 114(1), 43-63. Available at: https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/27549767.pdf?casa_token=M9JxrUaeyMoAAAAA:PGhCFROYntZILD3_-J1uUYXTMVpz5jPEN7iXh2t2lu_W5GETWalyNOwctIpP68qVuAc4WHj2v7g8v3CINkl_iHwg-ypupOGGZnyxlKCGhonZ6071_Q [Accessed 17th December 2024]

Weimann, R. (1978) Shakespeare and the popular tradition in the theater : studies in the social dimension of dramatic form and function. [Accessed 6th August 2024]

Wiles, D. (1987) Shakespeare's clown : actor and text in the Elizabethan playhouse. Cambridge [Cambridgeshire] ; New York : Cambridge University Press. Available at: <https://archive.org/details/shakespearesclow0000wile> [Accessed 18th July 2024]